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Acronyms and abbreviations

dMFA	-	Dynamic material flow analysis
ECOPT ²	-	Environmentally Constrained Optimization of Prospective Technology Transitions
IAM	-	Integrated assessment model
LCA	-	Life cycle assessment
LCC	-	Life cycle costing
LCSA	-	Life cycle sustainability assessment
MFA	-	Material flow analysis
SAF	-	Sustainability and circularity assessment framework
SD	-	System dynamics
S-LCA	-	Social life cycle assessment
SSPs	-	Shared socioeconomic pathways
TC	-	Transfer coefficient

1 Executive Summary

This document introduces a novel sustainability and circularity assessment framework (SAF) designed to assess circular transitions at the system level. Specifically, it will be applied to evaluate three key value chain circular transitions developed in the EU-funded TREASoURcE project. The report begins by outlining the objectives and specific requirements of the assessment in section 2. Then, section 3 reviews the available approaches for circularity and sustainability assessment at the system level, life cycle sustainability assessment, material flow analysis and system dynamics. Further, it explains how these approaches can be utilized for the specific needs of circular transitions. In section 4, these approaches are evaluated against criteria based on the assessment requirements (as they are defined in section 2). Finally, a novel SAF that combines the existing approaches in an innovative way to utilize their complementarity is proposed and detailed in section 5.

The novel SAF presented in this report overcomes challenges in current sustainability and circularity assessment approaches by integrating multiple approaches within a regulated framework. Inspired by the standard LCA application, the SAF encompasses four phases: goal & scope, data collection, results calculation, and interpretation. Each of these phases is described in detail in subsections *Phase 1: Defining the goal and scope*, *Phase 2: Data collection*, *Phase 3: Results calculation*, and *Phase 4: Interpretation*. Throughout the TREASoURcE project, the SAF will be applied to key value chains, fine-tuning and improving the novel approach for broader future application. This document is the first iteration of the final guidance and will be updated continuously throughout the project.

2 Objective of the assessment

The sustainability and circularity assessment framework (hereafter referred to as SAF) that is presented in this report is motivated by the objective of assessing the sustainability and circularity of a transition to a circular economy on a system level. Specifically, the circular economy transition is assessed for three key value chains, for which systemic changes are developed within the TREASoURcE project. This EU-funded project aims to initiate systemic change by developing systemic circular economy solutions in cities and regions for currently underutilised or unused plastic waste, end-of-life electric vehicle batteries and bio-based waste and side streams. In the context of the TREASoURcE project, the sustainability assessment approach especially looks at circular economy solutions at the regional level.

The transition to a circular economy necessitates robust and reliable sustainability assessments to ensure that economic, environmental, and social dimensions are comprehensively evaluated and balanced. Without such assessments, initiatives may fail to address key sustainability challenges or inadvertently create new problems. In this way, the fundamental objective of the circular economy transition, i.e., the reduction of the adverse impacts on the environment and society, would not be fulfilled. Furthermore, novel frameworks for such assessment need to be developed because traditional assessment methods often fall short in capturing the dynamic and interconnected nature of circular systems. The assessment of circular transitions on a system level requires a well-suited assessment approach, which should be reflected in the assessment framework. In general, the assessment framework should fulfil the following requirements:

- Comprehensive range of indicators addressing various aspects of sustainability, i.e., environmental, social, economic, as well as circular, and market indicators. In this way, the trade-off between individual impact categories can be revealed and the hidden burden shifting be prevented.
- Consideration of the specific context, i.e., characteristics of the assessed region.
- Consideration of the mechanisms that drive and determine the behaviour of the system in relation to the assessed value chains
- Predicting the development of the system over time, i.e., system-oriented prospective analysis.
- Analysis and modelling of the value chains on a granular level, i.e., on the level of individual unit processes.
- Region-specific sustainability thresholds
- Identification of the optimal transition pathway

In the following sections of the report, individual assessment approaches that can be utilized to inform the sustainability and circularity assessment of circular value chain transitions are first identified and described (section 3). In general, three assessment approaches are presented, (prospective) life cycle sustainability assessment, (dynamic) material flow analysis and system dynamics modelling. The strengths and limitations of these individual assessment approaches are then analysed (section 4). Then, a SAF developed for the assessment described above is introduced and described (section 5).

3 Sustainability and circularity assessment approaches

Three main approaches are commonly used for sustainability and circularity assessment and assessment of systems: Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), Dynamic Material Flow Analysis (dMFA), and System Dynamics (SD). LCSA integrates environmental, economic, and social dimensions, extending traditional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) (Guinée et al., 2011). It evaluates the sustainability performance of products, processes, or services over their entire life cycle, i.e., from raw material extraction to end of their life. The dMFA tracks the flow of materials through a system over time, e.g., providing insights into resource use and waste generation (Brunner et al., 2020), aspects important for the analysis of circular economy transitions. SD models the behaviour of complex systems over time, enabling the understanding of the interactions and dependencies within the system (Forrester, 1961).

Each approach has distinct characteristics that partially address specific assessment requirements (as they were defined in section 1). The following subsections introduce these assessment approaches in a greater detail. Furthermore, the discussion on how these approaches can be used for the assessment of circular value chain transitions developed in the TREASoURcE project is provided in the following subsections as well.

3.1 Life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA) and prospective LCSA

A commonly referred to definition for sustainable development is the one given by the Brundtland report. It defines sustainable development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (Brundtland, 1987). With this definition in mind, sustainability is about preserving a system by staying within certain boundaries, thereby not causing irreversible changes. Changes that would prevent future generations from living within the same system in which the current generation lives in. System stability can to a certain extent be ensured by not surpassing certain thresholds.

Sustainability assessments have typically been conducted using linear approaches. Life cycle assessment (LCA) has become the “standard” approach for modelling the impacts of products or services over the life cycle, from raw material extraction to production to end-of-life. Variants of LCA can be used to calculate the environmental impacts (environmental LCA or simply LCA), social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) to measure the social impacts, and life cycle costing (LCC) to assess the economic dimension. An often-cited formula for life cycle sustainability assessment (LCSA), with the combination of all three dimensions, is $LCA + S-LCA + LCC$. The approaches for assessing these three dimensions of sustainability (i.e., LCA, S-LCA and LCC) are discussed in the following subsections.

All three approaches for the assessment of the individual dimensions follow a general methodological framework consisting of four phases (based on ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006 standards):

1. Goal & scope definition
2. Inventory analysis
3. Impact assessment
4. Interpretation

3.1.1 Environmental sustainability - LCA

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a holistic method for calculating the environmental impacts of products and technologies. As the name implies, the method considers all life cycle phases of the product in question, from raw material extraction, manufacturing, use and disposal, e.g., from the product's "cradle-to-grave". This approach captures full impacts in contrast to approaches that only consider direct emissions from the use phase and thereby avoids misleading results from analyses that do not consider the full life cycle (International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 2006:14044). This approach allows evaluating the environmental performance of the study subject, identifying hotspots and trade-offs in impacts along its value chain.

Indicators used in LCA cover a wide breadth of environmental impact types, such as climate change, particulate matter formation, acidification, freshwater and marine eutrophication, toxicity and resource use (water, fossil, mineral). These indicators are grouped in composite indicators for areas of protection, for example, ecosystem health, human health and resource use (EC-JRC: European Commission-Joint Research Centre—Institute for Environment and Sustainability, 2010; Verones et al., 2020).

With this complete perspective of environmental impacts and the inclusion of the entire value chain, the aim of LCA is to provide a holistic understanding of the subject environmental impacts and understand where problem shifting and trade-offs may occur, either to other types of environmental effects or to other areas along the supply chain.

There are different methodological variants of LCA, each of which is suited to answering different questions (van der Giesen et al., 2020; Guinée et al., 2018). Prospective LCA considers environmental impacts at a future point in time and is particularly relevant to evaluate the potential impacts of commercializing emerging technologies. However, this requires assumptions regarding how the techno-economic development of the world will develop, affecting production systems and value chains, and thus resulting in higher uncertainty. Furthermore, there is not a current, single prescribed approach to how prospective LCA should be performed, resulting in the development of a number of different methods over the years (Adrianto et al., 2021; van der Giesen et al., 2020). Examples of these approaches include the use of forward-looking databases that account for upscaling dynamics, technological learning and; integration with energy scenario modelling and integrated assessment models (IAMs) that consider the wider energy system and socioeconomic contexts of the future; technological mapping & upscaling (Adrianto et al., 2021).

The standard LCA method evaluates the environmental impacts at the product level and assumes linearity and unconstrained upscaling. Consequently, the method is generally poorly suited to evaluating macro-level environmental impacts, such as the effects of introducing emerging technologies; systemic conditions, such as the lack of efficiencies of scale in manufacturing, effects of immature markets and underdeveloped supply chains on deployment are therefore not considered in product-level LCAs. Paradoxically, performing an environmental evaluation such as LCA would have the greatest influence on the technology development when performed early in the development and commercialization phases and has at this phase the most potential to inform the strategy for technology development and deployment with the greatest environmental benefits.

3.1.1.1 Prospective macro-scale modelling of technologies

The Environmentally Constrained Optimization of Prospective Technology Transitions (ECOPT²) generalized modelling framework was developed to address this gap in the standard LCA approach for the systemic evaluation of emerging technologies (Hung et al., 2022). The framework is presented in Figure 1. Furthermore, ECOPT² also identifies the environmentally optimal deployment pathway for such technologies while considering systemic conditions such as background system transformation, geographical differences, resource and manufacturing bottlenecks and consumer willingness to adopt. While consequential LCA (CLCA) is an approach to investigate the environmental impacts of decisions, the method mostly prescribes the use of marginal suppliers which are appropriate for local or small-scale changes, but not for global transitions to new technologies.

At its core, ECOPT² is a linear optimization model with environmental impact as the objective function. The modeller adds system constraints such as supply chain parameters, manufacturing capacity,

societal willingness-to-uptake, demand-driven stock dynamics and composition which the model must respect in its solution. Exogenous scenario inputs include assumed future development of the energy system, and service demand (e.g., transport) which may be based, e.g., on the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs, Riahi et al., 2017). ECOPT2 then calculates the life cycle impacts of the technology fleet satisfying the required service level, following the principle of a functional unit from LCA. The output of the model is the regionalized technology diffusion pathway leading to the lowest overall emissions or environmental impact from providing the service.

Figure 1: Structure of ECOPT2 model framework (Hung et al., 2022)

Standard LCAs are also often static "snapshots" in time, whether describing the current state-of-the-art, or a prospective product in the future. However, the analysis of transformation pathways requires consideration of the temporal perspective, and thereby includes the transformation of the background system, such as the introduction of new electricity-generating technologies, and a consideration of the cumulative environmental effects in the period.

An additional feature of ECOPT2 is the identification of the optimal solution and automated running of scenario analyses. Instead of isolating key parameters to run sensitivity analyses one at a time, ECOPT2 is able to automate the running of analyses using all combinations of parameter values for comparison, allowing the identification of important parameter combinations and evaluating the robustness of results to system conditions. Additionally, the use of linear optimization identifies the environmentally most beneficial solution through variation of key parameters, thus eliminating the risk of not identifying the scenario leading to minimal environmental impacts through single-variable tweaking. Further details regarding the technical implementation and structuring of ECOPT2 is published in Hung et al. (2022).

3.1.2 Economic sustainability - LCC

The life cycle costing (LCC) is the basis of the assessment of the economic sustainability dimension of the system. It is an economic assessment method used to evaluate the total cost associated with the assessed value chain. It encompasses all costs incurred during all value chain activities that belong to the system boundary of the assessed system (production cost, use cost, disposal cost, recycling cost, etc.). LCC helps in understanding the long-term economic implications of implementing circular value chains on a system level.

3.1.2.1 Prospective LCC

Prospective LCC analysis aims to forecast future costs of the value chain activities. The steps for conducting a prospective LCC analysis include:

- Step 1: Analysis of cost development trends
- Step 2: Expert Validation
- Step 3: Inflation Adjustment

Step 1: Analysis of Cost Development Trends

The first step involves grouping costs into specific categories based on the product category or sector. It is important that the costs are grouped according to their similar relationship to expected future cost drivers. For example, costs can be categorized into specific groups of production inputs: electricity, polymeric materials, metals, etc. Grouping the inputs in this way will make the prospective analysis more time-efficient, while the future development predictions are sufficiently precise.

Next, a comprehensive review of existing literature and models on the future development of prices for the identified cost categories is conducted. This includes examining studies, reports, and databases that provide forecasts and trends. If there is insufficient information available, an analysis of historical trends and their extrapolation should be performed. When an extrapolation is carried out, it is important to also assess the context of the specific cost category. To assess the cost category

context, the key factors that can be expected to drive the changes in a given cost category should be mapped. The possible future impact of these factors on the cost category should then be investigated.

A scenario definition is then conducted to develop scenarios based on different assumptions about future changes in cost drivers. The scenarios should be designed to capture the whole range of possible outcomes, considering aspects such as technological advancement, regulation or global economic development.

Step 2: Expert Validation

The second step involves validating the findings from the previous step by consulting relevant stakeholders and experts if such validation is feasible. This can be done through interviews or surveys to gather insights on the expected development of costs in the future and the key factors that will drive this development. Especially the extrapolated trends should be compared with the insights provided by the experts to identify possible discrepancies and rectify the projections.

Step 3: Inflation Adjustment

This step involves adjusting for inflation to express future costs in current monetary terms. The future inflation rates for the chosen currency (e.g., Euro) can be collected from central banks or official financial and economic institutions. These collected future inflation rates should then be applied to the predicted future costs to ensure that projected costs reflect their real value in the future, accounting for the time value of money.

3.1.3 Social sustainability – S-LCA

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is a comprehensive methodology designed to evaluate the social impacts associated with the lifecycle of a product or service. Unlike traditional life cycle assessments that primarily focus on environmental impacts, S-LCA extends the evaluation to encompass social aspects, ensuring a more holistic approach to sustainability. While not being identical with the environmental life cycle assessment methodology, the S-LCA methodology aligns with the main principles outlined in the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards. The LCA framework presented in these standards consisting of 4 phases (goal & scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretation) is well suited for the S-LCA as well (as also established in the UNEP's Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessments of Products and Organizations (UNEP, 2020)).

Goal & scope definition

In this first phase of the S-LCA, the reason for carrying out the assessment, i.e., the goal of the study, should be defined. Alongside, the scope of the study aligning with the goal should be defined. The scope definition, as per the Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessments of Products and Organizations (UNEP, 2020), has to generally address the following aspects:

- Functional unit and reference flow
- System boundaries
- Product system
- Activity variable
- Stakeholders included in the assessment
- Impact assessment method and indicators assessed
- Data collection and quality
- Allocation process
- Assumptions, limitations and planned interpretation

Many of these aspects are determined during the scope definition within the first phase of the application of the sustainability and circularity framework presented in this report. The aspects specific to the S-LCA scope are discussed below in more detail.

S-LCA can consider various social impact categories, which target various stakeholder groups. Each social impact category has social indicator(s) that reflect the state of a specific social aspect that the impact category relates to. For instance, one of the social impact categories assessed could be child labor, which can have a social indicator of hours of missed education. The concept of stakeholder groups, i.e., groups of stakeholders with similar interest based on their similar relationship to the assessed product system, is used to categorize the stakeholders. Furthermore, The selection of the social impact categories is an important step of the goal and scope phase of the S-LCA and should be based on the stakeholder and expert inputs. The social impact categories classified according to the specific stakeholder group are referred to as “subcategories”. According to the UNEP Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessments of Products and Organizations (UNEP, 2020), all relevant stakeholders and impact categories should be included in the S-LCA. Moreover, the impact assessment method should be specified, with the two main approaches being reference scale assessment or impact pathway assessment methods. The reference scale assessment approach is recommended to be used in the framework presented in this report.

An important component of S-LCA is the activity variable, which represents the quantifiable measure of an activity related to a unit process. It is used in the quantification of the impacts, as it expresses the relative share of a specific unit process within the whole assessed product system. An activity variable that is commonly used is worker hour(s), i.e., time that a worker spends carrying out a specific activity (related to a unit process). In this case, the contribution of a specific unit process to the impacts of the whole product system would be determined based on the share of the worker hours of the specific unit process within the total worker hours of the whole product system.

Inventory Analysis

This phase of the S-LCA involves steps such as prioritization of data to be collected from primary sources and actual data collection from primary and secondary sources. The inventory established for the value chain activities within the assessed system is to be used for the assessment of social indicators, analogously to the assessment of the environmental indicators. However, additional data points need to be collected when assessing social sustainability. Namely, for the reference scale approach taken for the social impact assessment in the presented framework these datapoints are:

- the activity variables for individual unit processes (value chain activities) within the assessed system
- the data for establishing reference scales
- the data on the social indicators of individual unit processes (value chain activities) within the assessed system

Secondary sources are proposed to be primarily used for the collection of the aforementioned datapoints. The main secondary sources are expected to be S-LCA databases such as PSILCA or SOCA. These databases provide the activity variable information as well as the social performance of the unit processes (which is classified in relation to various subcategories) and reference scale information.

Impact assessment

The impact assessment phase is carried out to calculate and evaluate the potential social impacts. The potential social impacts refer to a probable presence of a social impact as a result of the activities associated with the assessed system. Since the potential social impacts are based on background data, they are burdened with a certain level of uncertainty and should not be considered absolute (UNEP, 2020).

The social reference assessment approach is the social impacts assessment method recommended in this framework. The main advantage of this approach is the availability of the theoretical models and information necessary for the evaluation of a broad range of social indicators. The reference scale assessment approach is carried out following these main steps (UNEP, 2020):

1. Establishment of the reference scales (Reference scales qualify the social performance or social risk by qualifying it as one of the reference scale levels. The reference scale levels are based on performance reference points, which are targets/thresholds set to indicate the magnitude of potential social impacts. The performance reference points are typically set based on standards, legislation of best practices)
2. Assessing the social indicator data from the inventory against the reference scales to assign the reference scale levels.
3. Assessing the social impacts of the whole product system by applying the activity variable. The activity variable is used to determine the relative contribution of individual unit processes to the overall social impacts of the whole product system.

3.1.3.1 Prospective Social Life Cycle Assessment Method

To carry out the S-LCA with a prospective perspective, primarily the inventory analysis phase of the S-LCA framework needs to be adjusted. More specifically, the values for the social indicators and activity variable can be expected to change in the future, especially for emerging and upscaled technology. Hence, a methodology to perform this inventory analysis adjustment to take possible future changes of the inventory into account is proposed within this framework. This method can be generally categorized as consisting of two prospective analyses:

- Prospective analysis of social conditions
- Prospective analysis of activity variables

Prospective analysis of social conditions

This analysis is proposed to be used for predicting of the social conditions (i.e., the values of social indicators) related to the social impact categories assessed. The main steps of the analysis are outlined below:

1. Identification and mapping of the driving factors
2. Selection of key driving factors
3. Establishment of the mathematical relationships between the driving factors and social conditions
4. Prediction of the future development of the driving factors and social conditions

Step 1: Identification and mapping of the driving factors:

- The potential driving factors that generally influence social conditions are identified by conducting a comprehensive review of existing literature. This review should cover academic articles, industry reports, policy documents, and other relevant sources. The aim is to gather a wide range of data and insights on factors such as economic trends, policy changes, technological advancements, and cultural shifts. Another source of information for identifying the potential driving factors of social conditions are estimates and judgments of experts in the relevant fields. These experts can provide valuable insights based on their experience and knowledge, supplementing the findings from the literature review. Methods such as interviews, surveys, and Delphi techniques can be used to collect expert opinions.
- The second part of this step aims to map the links between the identified driving factors and assessed social conditions. Creating a visual map with all driving factors, social conditions and links between them might help to understand how each factor affects different social conditions. For instance, economic growth may influence labour conditions by affecting employment rates and wage levels, while technological advancements might impact worker safety and skill requirements.

Step 2: Selection of key driving factors

- In this step, the key driving factors defined in the previous step are refined to select the ones to use further in the prospective analysis. The selection process is based on assessing each of the driving factors according to two criteria: *influence* and *measurability*. A three-level scale (low, medium, high) is used to qualify the driving factors according to these criteria. The *influence* criterion assesses the extent to which each driving factor can impact social conditions. High-influence factors are those that have a significant effect on social indicators and are therefore crucial for the assessment. The *measurability* criterion evaluates how easily changes in each driving factor can be measured and monitored. Factors with high observability are those for which reliable data are readily available. The basis for evaluating the driving factors against these two criteria is information available in the literature and expert judgement.
- Based on the scores assigned to each driving factors, the driving factors are prioritised. The most significant driving factors that have high influence and measurability are selected for further analysis. This ensures that the prospective analysis will focus on the most impactful and measurable factors, making the assessment more efficient and effective. Furthermore, the selection of the key driving factors to consider for the prospective analysis should be aligned with the scenarios defined during the goal and scope phase of the assessment. For instance, if there would be a scenario assuming that no change to the economic stability of the assessed region would occur, the driving factor of the economic stability could be excluded from the prospective analysis.

Step 3: Establishment of the mathematical relationships between the driving factors and social conditions

In this step, the relationships between the selected driving factors and the social conditions they influence are defined and quantified. This involves establishing causal links and understanding how changes in driving factors translate to social impacts. Since the driving factors and social conditions are a part of complex real-world systems, no single modelling approach might be sufficient to represent the relationships within these systems holistically. However, there reality-simplifying approaches that can be applied to model the relationships with sufficient confidence and within reasonable time. Three of such approaches are presented below. It is important to stress that the selection (with a possible adjustment) of the approach for establishing the relationships between the social conditions and driving factors is up to the modeller's judgement. The selection of the approach should be based on the specifics of the system that is being modelled, considering the practical aspects of applying the approach such as data availability and time intensity.

- **First Approach: Parameter-Based Relationship Establishment**

In this approach, the relationships are conceptualized via the use of specific parameters. Namely, the considered parameters are the change in the value of the driving factor, connectivity and sensitivity. Change of the driving factor expresses the magnitude of change of a specific driving factor. The connectivity determines the likelihood that a change in a driving

factor will affect a social condition. Determining connectivity involves estimating the probability that a given change in the driving factor will lead to a specific social impact. Sensitivity expresses the magnitude of the impact that a change in the driving factor will have on the social condition. It can be estimated based on literature review and regression analysis. The change of a specific social condition can be expressed in relation to the change of each of the key driving factors in this way. To calculate the final change in the social condition, as per changes in all driving factors, the changes of the social conditions calculated for the change of each driving factors are combined.

- **Second Approach: Regression Analysis**

In this approach a regression analysis is carried out to express the relationship between the social condition (treated as a dependent variable) and a driving factor (treated as an independent variable). One of the possible approaches would be to carry out a single regression for each driving factor and social condition. In this case an assumption of ceteris paribus has to be made. In such cases, evidence justifying the ceteris paribus assumption is desirable to be provided. Another approach is to carry out a multiple regression, treating the social condition as a dependent variable and all of the key driving factors as independent variables and parameters of the regression equation.

- **Third approach: Level-based probability distribution functions**

This approach makes use of the fact that the social risk is expressed in discrete risk level values. In this approach the probability distribution function is determined for each of the risk levels first. This distribution function is established based on the [social condition, driving factor] datapoints available for each pair of social condition and driving factor. Ideally, the obtained probability distribution can be fitted by one of the common distribution functions (e.g., normal distribution, log-normal distribution etc.). In this way, a set of probability distribution functions is determined with each function representing one risk level on the reference scale of a specific social impact. Following this approach, a set of probability distribution functions is defined for each of the social condition and driving factor pairs. As a result, a probability of a specific risk level can be calculated for based on chosen values of all key driving factors. Then, the risk level with highest probability can be chosen as representative. Additionally, this approach allows to express the uncertainty of specific risk levels assigned based on the probability it is associated with. In this way, the uncertainty is specific to the risk level rather than the whole model (which is the case for regression analysis). When applying this approach, it is important to consider the interdependencies between the driving factors, analyze whether these dependencies are being ignored and evaluate if this could introduce a bias to the assessment.

Step 4: Prediction of the future development of the driving factors and social conditions

In this final step of the prospective analysis of social conditions, the future development of the driving factors is determined and then the future social conditions corresponding to the driving factor future development are evaluated. The future development of the key driving factors can be based on the information found in the expert literature such as scientific papers, industry reports, etc. Additionally,

the future development of the driving factors can be based on the extrapolation of the historical data. However, when using extrapolation, it is important to assess whether there are any factors driving the development of the driving factors that would undergo significant changes unparalleled in the historical developments. Furthermore, the third source of information for the prediction of the future development of driving factors is expert judgement. It is also recommendable to use the expert judgement in along with other approaches to validate the predictions made.

Once the future development of the driving factors is determined (along with the corresponding uncertainty), the predicted future values of driving factors will be used to determine the corresponding social conditions. Regardless of the relationship-establishment method that was used in the previous step, the future driving factor values (or their change) will be used as parameters in the function that determines the future social conditions.

Prospective analysis of activity variable

The approach towards conducting the prospective analysis of the activity variable is significantly dependent on the variable chosen. The activity variable considered to be used within the S-LCA within the presented framework is *worker hours* variable. The prediction of the future development of the activity variable can be based on the review of the existing literature, expert judgement as well as on the extrapolation of the historical trends. When conducting the analysis, the main factors influencing the worker hours should be identified and considered. If feasible, the predicted future activity variable values should be validated by relevant stakeholders. As evaluating the development of the activity variable for all processes within the assessed value chain would be a very time-consuming task, it is recommendable to start with the prospective analysis of the activity variable on the sector and country level.

3.2 Material flow analysis (MFA) and dynamic MFA

MFA is a systematic approach to assessing the flows and stocks of materials through a system within a defined spatial and temporal boundary (Brunner et al., 2020). Materials can be both a substance and a good. A process is defined as the transformation, transport, or storage of one or more materials. Stocks mean the total amount of materials which is stored in a process, usually it is in the consumption phase. A flow is defined as the actual exchange of materials determined for a system in units (e.g., ton/year). A system boundary is determined by the types of materials and processes to be included in the analysis, spatial boundaries for the study, and the temporal interval for which the study is to be conducted.

The fundamental principle of MFA is the mass balance principle: Inflows into an MFA system equal the outflows plus changes in stocks to consider accumulation and depletion (Allesch and Brunner 2015). All processes within the system are balanced according to the mass balance principle. The given system can be static with discrete time and continuous over multiple timepoints, resulting in two

types of MFA - static MFA and dynamic MFA (dMFA) (Barkhausen et al., 2023). If an MFA describes a “snapshot” of a system in time, it is static; if it describes the behaviour of a system over a time interval, it is dynamic (Chen et al., 2012). In the dMFA, inflows or stocks are used as input variables for accounting, and then the remaining two variables are projected by assuming the possible average lifetimes and lifetime distributions of inflows (Deng et al., 2023). Accordingly, dynamic material flow accounting has been divided into stock-driven and flow-driven approaches (Wiedenhofer et al., 2019).

MFA can be either retrospective (or historical), prospective or a combination of both approaches (Müller et al., 2014). Historical models usually assess the yearly material flows in the system by analyzing past stocks and flows based on historical data. Prospective modelling is future-oriented to assess scenarios and use data extrapolation by modelling future material flows over long time periods and includes stock-driven and inflow-driven models. Stock-driven model uses the in-use stock as the main driver of a material cycle, especially for materials with a long lifetime. Past stocks are first calculated using an input-driven model; then the stocks are extrapolated to finally calculate future inflows using a stock-driven model (B. Müller, 2006). Inflow-driven model uses the assumed input flows to predict the waste flows. It is usually used in cases when past stock showed no clear pattern, or in cases when in-use stock is estimated as zero, such as bio-waste stream. The equations for both historical and prospective models are further stated in step 3 historical mapping of stocks and flows and step 4 projective modelling of this section. In recent years, Material Flow Analysis (MFA) has been used extensively in waste management to quantify flows and stocks of materials through society, such as plastics (Joosten, Hekkert, and Worrell, 2000), metals (Müller et al., 2014), electronic waste (Islam and Huda, 2019), etc.

The TREASoURcE project focuses on three waste streams, i.e., plastic waste, Bio-waste, and EV battery waste. For each waste stream, dynamic MFA is utilized to map the material cycle and assess the waste generation overtime, and the process includes the following four steps:

- Step 1. System definition (including scope, monitoring indicators selections, boundaries, and timeframe)
- Step 2. Data collection and process (e.g., identification of flows, processes and stocks, and associated data sources)
- Step 3. Historical mapping of stocks and flows (e.g., quantification of flows and stocks based on the data compiles and mass balance principle)
- Step 4. Scenario development and prospective modelling

3.2.1 Step 1: System definition

System definition is the first and key step to map MFA. It is crucial to define the temporal, spatial, and/or thematic system boundaries. Usually, the temporal boundary uses the year as a unit and it is tailored for the different waste streams, as each stream depends on the availability of the most recent data. The spatial boundary can be geographical, hydrological, or administrative boundaries (Allesh et

al., 2015). The thematic system boundaries can be further categorized geographically, such as global, continents, countries, regions, or cities.

In the report, the general system definition (Figure 1) usually includes four main phases from material production to fabrication & manufacturing, then to consumption (use) before waste management & recycling.

Figure 2: System overview of a generic dynamic material flow model.

As shown in Figure 2, the materials from production first enter the fabrication & manufacturing phase, and then the use phase. After the consumption, stock is accumulated and stored over time and the generated waste flows go to the waste management phase after the product service lifetime. Trade (i.e., imports and exports) at different phases are also shown in Figure 2 and a small part of material is lost as waste and enters the environment. Figure 2 is used here to show an example of the system boundaries, flows, stocks, processes and losses. The system definition has subtle differences in different cases and will be further elaborated specifically for each waste stream in the report.

3.2.2 Step 2: Data collection & processing

Dynamic MFA is used to map the material cycle along the supply chain (as shown in Figure 2). Generally, it assumes that no material is stored in the phases of production, manufacturing, and waste management & recycling. The inflows to the next phase are the outflows from the previous phase, based on the principles of mass conservation. It is the consumption (or use) phase that dynamic MFA focuses on, as the in-use stock in the phase changes over time. After the service lifetime of these stocks, waste streams are generated, which can be quantified by dynamic MFA model (detailed in Step 3).

In order to quantify the waste streams (i.e., outflows from the consumption phase), long-time series of the consumption data (i.e., inflows to the consumption phase) are considered, but they are usually difficult to obtain from existing sources. If the consumption data are not available, dynamic MFA usually considers simulated apparent consumption as the consumption data. The apparent consumption is

determined by production plus imports and minus exports and losses. The equations for the apparent consumption are further stated in step 3 historical mapping of stocks and flows in this section.

Usually, data used in dynamic MFA can be either collected or processed. The data collected are compiled from multiple sources: official databases, peer-reviewed publications, expert opinions, and gray literature. Where these data are missing for a particular year, they are either linearly interpolated between existing estimates or set to the nearest data point if interpolation is not possible. They include:

- 1) Inflows in the phases of material production and fabrication & manufacturing;
- 2) Transfer coefficients (TCs), which are used to describe the partitioning of the mass from one phase to the next;
- 3) Imports and exports in various phases of a given system.

Data processed include outflows and losses in various phases of the given system as well as stocks generated in the consumption phase. They are calculated in different ways, as follows.

- a) Outflow data are quantified by assigning lifetime distribution functions to specific material or end-use phases, with the relationship between inflows and outflows;
- b) In-use stocks in year t are determined by the initial stock and annual net stocks that equal inflow minus outflow over the past T years. If a given year (e.g., 1998) has the earliest available data, the initial material in-use stocks of end use before this year (e.g., 1998) is assumed to be negligible;
- c) Losses are usually estimated by multiplying the inflow mass by the loss rate (a TCs). In waste management & recycling phase, TCs are also used, where the mass in each compartment is multiplied by the corresponding TCs to obtain the mass in the following compartments (Anis et al. 2013). For example, the mass of incineration is calculated as the mass of recycled material multiplied by the TCs.

3.2.3 Step 3: Historical mapping of stocks and flows

Historical data (e.g., on long-term consumption) is often accessible, but waste flows from after use phase are rarely measured. In order to quantify the waste stream, the first step is to calculate apparent consumption (i.e., material flows into the consumption phase), then to calculate in-use stocks which accumulate over the time. Finally, both apparent consumption data and in-use stock data are used to quantify the waste stream. The equations (eqs) are as follows.

With the aim to quantify the apparent consumption, the calculation is shown as in eq 1.

$$\text{consumption}(t) = \text{production}(t) + \text{import}(t) - \text{export}(t) - \text{production}(t) * K(t) \quad (1)$$

where consumption represents apparent consumption, which means the material flows into the consumption phase, t is the requested year and $K(t)$ is the loss rate.

The top-down approach is used estimate in-use stocks, which derives the in-use stock S from the new flow by using the balance of masses as shown in eq 2.

$$S[T] = S[0] + \sum_{t=1}^T (consumption [t] - waste[t]) \quad (2)$$

where S[T] are the in-use stock in years T, S[0] are the in-use stock in initial year 0. Typically S[0] is assumed as zero, and t is the requested year. Consumption represents apparent consumption, waste after the use phase represents the retired products after a service lifetime.

With the aim to quantify waste stream, calculation is shown in eq 3.

$$waste [T] = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} consumption[t - n] * f[n] \quad (3)$$

where f[n] is the probability densities of the lifetime distribution function for the time discrete case, and consumption represents apparent consumption.

The most frequently used lifetime distribution functions most frequently are the Dirac delta distribution, which represents average and constant lifetime, and the Weibull distribution. Other distributions used are the normal, log-normal, beta, and gamma distributions. For each waste stream included in this report, the lifetime distribution functions have subtle differences and will be further elaborated specifically.

3.2.4 Step 4: Prospective modelling

Prospective modelling is used to assess scenarios by modelling future material flows over long time periods. Like historical mapping, apparent consumption is used to obtain the waste stream data. The difference is that in historical modelling, apparent consumption is based on historical data and in prospective modelling it is based on forecast data.

To predict consumption, two types of models can be applied, including stock-driven model and inflow-driven model. The selection of the two models is based on the patterns identified from historical mapping. If the historical mapping shows a clear trend of in-use stocks, the stock-driven model is selected. Otherwise, the inflow-driven model is selected. In most cases, the stock-driven model is considered first, but in some cases where the in-use stock from historical mapping does not show a clear pattern or there are no materials stocks (e.g., bio-waste), the inflow-driven model is selected.

For the stock-driven model, there are three main approaches to predict: growth curve models, time series models, and scenario modeling (Deng, Zhang, and Fu 2023). Growth curve models mostly use logistical growth curves and describe the limited growth phenomenon of the “S” growth curve. Time series models can effectively include historical development features. Scenario models make predictions based on reasonable scenarios, allowing a variety of prediction possibilities, not only for conventional scenarios but also for extreme cases. In the report, growth curve models are applied.

The prospective stocks and flows demand is determined by the lifetime distribution function and future stock patterns derived from population prospects and per capita stock assumptions, as shown in eq 4.

$$S(t) = \frac{K}{1 + \left(\frac{K}{S_0} - 1\right) * e^{-a*(t-t_0)}} \quad (4)$$

where $S(t)$ is the stock at requested year t , K is the assumed stock saturation level, S_0 is the initial stock, and a is a constant.

For inflow-driven model, the entire system dynamics is determined by the inflow of mass and lifetime functions, with a logistic function that takes growth limits of a system into account, as shown in eq 5.

$$\text{inflow}(t) = \frac{p_1}{1 + e^{-p_2 * (t - p_3)}} \quad (5)$$

with p_1 = saturation value of inflow [ton/year, for example], p_2 = steepness of the sigmoidal curve, and p_3 = midpoint of the growth trajectory. t = time. The parameters are determined using fitting algorithms (e.g., the ordinary least-squares method). There are other inflow-driven models, for example, as a function of socioeconomic explanatory variables, such as GDP, population size, product price, etc. but are not applied in the report.

3.3 System dynamics

System dynamics is an approach used for the modelling of complex systems, accounting for the causal structure and interconnectedness of the individual elements of the modelled system (Bala, Arshad, Noh, 2017). In general, the system dynamics models conceptualize the system under assessment as a collection of stocks, flows and auxiliary variables (Bala, Arshad, Noh, 2017). All of these elements and relationships between them are defined mathematically. Based on these relationships, the development of the values over the simulation time is calculated for each of the system elements.

Stocks represent the states of individual elements of the model in terms of quantity. They can accumulate or deplete over time, depending on the net rate of inflows and outflows. Collectively, they represent the state of the system at any given point in time. An example of a *stock* in the context of the sustainability assessment framework would be the stock of the *population of the region*.

Flows are the rates at which stocks change over time. They represent the activity or processes that increase or decrease the level of stocks. Since they are responsible for the change of stocks, they are the driver of the changes in the system. An example of the flow in the context of the sustainability assessment framework would be the flow of the *death rate* that would deplete the stock of the *population*.

Auxiliary variables are the parameters of a SD model that help to define and clarify more complex mathematical relationships between the elements of the model. They often represent constants or functions that influence the behaviour of flows and stocks or values of other variables. For instance,

an auxiliary variable of *cancer incidence* could be used to define the *death rate* flow with more precision.

SD models capture the dynamics of the system identifying elements that influence other elements of the system and creating links between these elements. SD models are often characterized by a high interconnectedness of individual elements of the system. The links between individual elements of a system often create feedback loops where the output of a (part of a) system influences its own input. Positive feedback loops reinforce changes (leading to exponential growth or decline), while negative feedback loops counteract changes in the system (leading to stabilization of the system). Thanks to this, SD models are able to capture the non-linear relationships in the model, which are impossible to capture with conventional LCA approaches.

3.3.1 Applying system dynamics to sustainability and circularity assessment

Applying system dynamics modelling to sustainability and circularity assessment involves a structured, iterative approach to capture the complexity and interdependencies of real-world systems. This method allows for a comprehensive analysis of how various elements interact over time, providing valuable insights for decision-making. The steps to take towards establishing a reliable SD model are presented below:

Step 1: Conceptualize the system

The first step is to conceptualize the system. This involves defining the main subsystems that are relevant to the sustainability and circularity assessment. Conceptualization helps to establish the boundaries of the system and identify key components and their interactions. By understanding the overarching structure and primary elements, we can set the stage for a detailed analysis of the system's dynamics.

Step 2: Specify Subsystems and Elements

In the second step, the subsystems and their elements based on available theoretical models and empirical observations are specified. This also includes determining the relationships between these elements. Several considerations are critical at this stage:

- **Activities associated with the value chain:** All activities related to the assessed circular economy value chains and associated should be incorporated into the model. This includes the states of the main stocks within the system, represented by accumulations of resources or products, and their modifications, represented by flows of products, materials or energy.
- **Sustainability impact and circularity indicators:** The indicators should be embedded within the model, while it should be ensured that sustainability impacts are generated endogenously as a result of the system's value chain activities. The indicators should reflect the sustainability of the system as comprehensively as possible, i.e., account for environmental, social and economic impacts as well as circularity of the system.

- **Constraining and driving factors:** Factors that constrain and drive value chain activities, such as market conditions and resource availability (both renewable and non-renewable), must be included. The market should be modelled dynamically, with supply and demand linked and responsive to real-time price developments, as market can be expected to be the driving factor of the value chain activities.
- **Context-specific indicators:** Specific indicators relevant to the system under assessment should also be considered to capture the unique characteristics and constraints of the system. These indicators should reflect region-specific aspects of the system under assessment, such as population.

Step 3: Iterative Model Development and Validation

The third step involves the iterative development of the model and validation. This process includes ongoing validation to test both the structure of the model and the behaviour it generates and use the information obtained from these tests to refine the model. Validation is crucial to ensure the model accurately reflects real-world dynamics and can reliably predict future states. Thanks to this approach, the reliability and robustness of the model can be assured.

Step 4: Application and Scenario Analysis

The final step is to apply the model by populating it with collected data and calculating the results. This involves carrying out an analysis of several scenarios to understand how different conditions and assumptions affect the system's behaviour. Since many elements of the system are heavily dependent on external factors that can change in the real world, it is essential to account for a wide range of possible situations. Scenario analysis allows stakeholders to explore potential outcomes and make informed decisions to enhance sustainability and circularity.

By following these steps, SD modelling provides a powerful tool for assessing and improving sustainability and circularity, enabling a deeper understanding of complex systems and more effective management of their long-term impacts.

4 Evaluation of the individual approaches

In this section, the individual assessment approaches described in section 3 are evaluated in terms of their suitability for the sustainability and circularity assessment of circular transitions on a system level. ECOPT², as presented in section 3.1.1.1, is evaluated here along with other approaches and distinguished from the traditional LCSA. The individual approaches are evaluated against the assessment requirements (criteria), as specified in section 2. The overview of the performance of the individual assessment approaches against these criteria is provided in Table 1. The following subsections feature a more detailed discussion on each of the criteria used for the evaluation of the approaches.

Table 1: Overview of the evaluation of the individual assessment approaches in relation to the assessment criteria.

Criterion	LCSA	ECOPT ²	MFA	SD
Context	Not considered	Partially considered	Not considered	Fully considered
System behavior driving mechanisms	Not considered	Partially considered	Not considered	Fully considered
Granular modelling of the value chain flows	Yes	Yes	Yes	Not feasible
Absolute sustainability thresholds	Possible to include	No	No	Possible to include
Prospective analysis	Yes, in prospective LCSA	Yes	Yes, in dynamic MFA	Yes
Comprehensive sustainability indicators	Yes	Environmental only	No	Yes (derived from LCSA)
Identification of optimal transition pathway	No	Yes	No	No

4.1 Absolute sustainability thresholds

LCSA approaches are meant to support relative assessments of sustainability, allowing for comparisons, to identify whether one life cycle has a higher or lower impact than another. Yet, sustainability essentially refers to a system that needs to be preserved, meaning not exceeding certain boundaries. Taking a literal definition of sustainability, thresholds need to be introduced, allowing for the assessment of sustainability in an absolute sense, which is traditionally not done in LCSA. Including e.g. the concept of planetary boundaries enables such an assessment approach (Sala et al., 2020). Similarly, such thresholds can also be used when assessing the sustainability in the SD model.

4.2 Context

A limitation of LCSA and MFA is that the context in which the life cycle and material flows take place is often not considered. LCSA studies often conclude with recommendations with limited feasibility and effectiveness because the regional context is not considered. Context indicators such as resource availability, population willingness to change, supporting infrastructure, volatility of local markets, etc. Putting the recommendations into context allows one to gain insights into the barriers and success factors of sustainability strategies. SD modelling is advantageous in this regard, as it allows the modeller to include the individual context indicators and relate them to the other elements of the system. Similarly, ECOPT² incorporates some of the context indicators relevant for the assessed value chains, such as production capacity.

4.3 System structure and driving mechanisms

Then, LCSA studies are typically conducted starting from a benefit which is provided by the investigated product or service. They then follow the supply chain and different life cycle processes linked to this product or service, going stepwise from one process to the next. In these steps, the overall system structure is not visible; rather, when interpreting results, insights are sought to be obtained about the importance of different life cycle stages. The LCSA approach thus typically does not integrate system knowledge into the modelling, apart from an ex-ante exclusion of different parts of the life cycle. The typical LCSA method also looks at the sustainability dimensions individually and does not consider their underlying relationship. Not considering the burden transfer across sustainability indicators may mislead decision-making (Li et al., 2023). Similarly, (dynamic) MFA typically uses exogenously defined flow rates without considering the causal structure of the system if refers to and mechanisms that drive its behaviour. Both approaches are traditionally based on a static or linear perspective, lacking the ability to account for changes of external factors over time. They assume steady conditions, which can misrepresent the actual dynamics of the system.

On the other hand, SD can incorporate non-linear interactions and thresholds, capturing the complexities of real-world systems where small changes can have significant impacts. Moreover, in contrast to traditional LCSA and dMFA, SD models can capture feedback loops, accounting for the modelling of complex interdependencies within the system. Furthermore, they can incorporate non-linear interactions and thresholds, capturing the complexities of real-world systems where small changes can have significant impacts. ECOPT² model incorporates the mechanisms driving the system behaviour partially, as it considers, e.g., the technology uptake rate and its influence on the assessed value chain.

4.4 Prospective analysis

LCSA and MFA studies are typically conducted in a static manner, with changes over time typically not being considered. Yet, in reality, the systems in which solutions are implemented are constantly changing, which essentially speaks for a dynamic and prospective assessment approach. To address this need, LCSA and MFA methodologies are adjusted to prospective LCSA and dynamic MFA. The ECOPT² tool incorporates the prospective analysis, as it is based on prospective LCA. Additionally, the SD models incorporate the prospective analysis fully, as they simulate the evolution of systems over time, allowing for the analysis of how changes in one part of the system propagate through to others over time.

4.5 Comprehensive sustainability indicators

The traditional LCSA provides valuable insights into the sustainability of products and processes, as it incorporates indicators related to environmental, social and economic sustainability. In this way, it allows for a comprehensive assessment of the sustainability. SD models can incorporate a comprehensive set of sustainability indicators derived from exogenous sources, such as LCSA. The ECOPT² allows for the assessment of environmental sustainability, but it lacks the social and economic dimension. MFA does not allow assessment of any of the sustainability indicators directly but it allows analysis of the circularity of the value chains based on the corresponding material flows.

4.6 Granular modelling of the value chain flows

To ensure that the assessed system is represented correctly, it is necessary to model the individual flows and activities constituting the system on a granular, disaggregated, level (corresponding to individual unit processes). Such modelling is characteristic of LCSA, MFA and ECOPT² approaches. On the other hand, SD models conceptualize the value chains on a more aggregated level, as relevant to the structure of the modelled system. While creating an SD model on the level of unit processes would be theoretically possible, it is usually not practically feasible.

4.7 Identification of the optimal transition pathway

The ECOPT² is the only approach that allows the identification of the optimal transition pathway. The objective function it optimizes is related to the environmental impacts associated with the assessed value chain. Hence, the optimal transition pathway identified represents the greatest potential reduction of environmental impacts. On the other hand, neither LCSA, MFA, nor SD approaches allow identification of the optimal transition pathways.

4.8 Summary

As discussed above, each of the assessment approaches has its peculiar strengths and limitations, while none fulfils all of the assessment requirements. Thus, it is essential to integrate Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), Material Flow Analysis (MFA), System Dynamics (SD), and ECOPT² approaches due to their complementary strengths. LCSA offers a comprehensive assessment of sustainability but lacks the consideration for the specific context of the assessed system. Incorporating SD models can address this by incorporating context indicators and capturing non-linear interactions and feedback loops present in the system, which are missed in LCSA and MFA's linear perspectives. In this way, the development of the whole system over time can be predicted. The MFA and LCSA provide detailed, granular modelling of value chains, which is essential for correct representation of the system in the assessment process. ECOPT² further complements other approaches by identifying optimal transition pathways, focusing on minimizing environmental impacts. Thus, using all four approaches jointly ensures a holistic, context-aware, prospective and dynamic assessment that integrates comprehensive sustainability indicators and system structures. All of these aspects are crucial for understanding long-term sustainability and circularity impacts of the systemic circular transitions.

Hence, an opportunity to develop a more extensive and dynamic assessment approach arises for the cases looked at in the TREASoURcE project and out of the limitations and complementarity mentioned above. The nonlinearity of circular economy solutions requires a such a systemic assessment approach (Franco, 2019). Therefore, a novel SAF was developed and is presented in the next section (section 5).

5 Novel sustainability and circularity assessment framework

The following document describes a novel SAF developed. The SAF helps identify hotspots, patterns, risks, and chances for the circular economy solutions developed in the TREASoURcE project. It takes on a novel approach to sustainability assessments and applies system dynamics linked to (prospective) life cycle sustainability assessments (LCSA) and (dynamic) material flow analysis (MFA) within a tailored and holistic framework. As discussed in section 4, the combination of the three approaches (including ECOPT² as a special approach based on LCSA) under the umbrella of a framework can help to overcome some of their shortcomings and at the same time allow for synergies to emerge. Thanks to this, suitable recommendations for effective circular economy solutions can be generated. This document specifies principles, requirements and guidelines for the application of this SAF.

The purpose of the SAF is to assess the sustainability impacts, circularity and the developments of a value chain in a systematic and dynamic manner. It essentially acts as a decision-making support tool that helps stakeholders, such as policy makers or businesses, make good decisions regarding possible circular economy strategies.

The SAF consists of four phases: a goal and scope definition, data collection, results calculation and interpretation. The procedure of applying the SAF follows an iterative process, where different steps of the SAF are continuously revised depending on insights gained throughout the assessment. The general SAF and the relationship between the phases are similar to the framework applied for life cycle assessments (LCA) (ISO 14040; ISO 14044) and is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Overview of the phases of the novel SAF.

A closer look at the individual phases shows that the application of the phases varies when compared to those of an LCA. The individual phases of the SAF are visualised in a greater detail in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Detailed overview of the SAF.

The scope has additional steps, such as defining a model structure as well as identifying relevant strategies in line with the goal. Furthermore, data collection is linked to LCSA and MFA, yet the main calculation tool applies system dynamics. The results are validated with a fine-tuned approach and additionally classified with a sustainability index.

The goal of the assessment describes the reason for carrying out the study. The scope shall clearly outline the extent of the study. It consists of several parts, including the value chain system boundaries, regional boundaries, types of materials and products, timeframe, indicator types and metrics, data requirements and assumptions, model structure adjustments, as well as the definition of the scenarios that are to be assessed. The goal and scope of the study may be revised due to unforeseen limitations, constraints or because of additional information (ISO 14040; ISO 14044).

Data collection commences once the goal and scope have initially been defined. The extent of the data requirements depends on the previously defined scope. The collected data is then transferred into the assessment tools for results calculation. In some cases, results are first calculated or collected in one tool (e.g. MFA and LCSA) and then transferred into the SD model for final calculation. MFA is used to collect the initial material and product flow quantities per life cycle stage. Dynamic MFAs typically predict the change of the material and product flow quantities over time based on historical trends. The SD model will predict these changes based on the specified model structure and integrated equations that define the relationship among the different elements of the model. The results of the dynamic MFA and the SD model will be compared as a validation measure.

The SD model forms the backbone of the SAF presented hereby. It has a central position within the framework, combining the information on material flows (incorporated from MFA), information on the impacts of the activities comprising the assessed value chains and their development in time (obtained from prospective LCSA) and information on the behaviour of the system (calculated directly within the SD model). The impact factors are taken from LCSA calculations using the LCSA software openLCA. The impact factors are for now manually transferred from the LCSA tool into the system dynamics model. As impact factors change over time due to e.g. technological developments, prospective LCSA is applied to quantify these changes. Thanks to its comprehensive nature, the SD model enables

generation of results that account for important factors that drive the behaviour of the system under assessment. Hence, it is very well-suited for the assessment of systemic solutions.

Figure 5: Overview of the interaction of the different tools.

Figure 5 shows again how the SD model interacts with (dynamic) MFA and (prospective) LCSA. The system definition of the applied MFA and the goal & scope of the LCSA can be derived from the defined goal & scope of this SAF.

Results calculation takes on 3 stages: applying the tools (MFA, LCSA and system dynamics), validating the results, and classifying the results. Validation will take on several different tests that aim to confirm the stability of the model and thus the reliability of the results. A sustainability index will categorize the results on a scale, thereby giving an indication on the extensiveness of the assessment.

The interpretation accompanies the assessment across all phases. The idea is to review preliminary findings and results and adjust the modelling decisions if needed. Once the model is fine-tuned sufficiently, the final results are interpreted thoroughly. In general, the interpretation phase consists of making key observations, an analysis of the results, a sensitivity analysis, a consideration of the trade-offs in light of the results for each strategy option, and finally the strategy recommendations.

First, the individual tools are introduced, followed by a detailed description and guidance of the whole SAF.

The following segments will go into a deeper explanation of the phases of the framework. The phases are closely interlinked, and the iterative nature of the framework makes it a vigorous approach. Furthermore, the results and depth of the assessment may vary significantly, depending on the scope defined by the modeller. This is why, for one, pathways are constructed during the assessment and second, the validation and classification administer the modellers flexibility and ensures a degree of precision.

The goal e.g. indicates what products will need to be assessed, what indicators are important, and even which circular economy strategies will be assessed. The scope determines more closely what data is needed but also constructs the system dynamics model structure. Modelling decisions thus lay out a pathway that ultimately lead to the desired end results. Again, later phases of the assessment might make it necessary to review previous steps, hence the iterative nature. The validation and classification also are constructed based on the assessment pathway. Yet, at this point, some principles are evaluated. This essentially gives the modeller and target audience some indication on the relevance, reliability and representativeness of the results.

5.1 Phase 1: Defining the goal and scope

The first step of an LCA is the definition of the goal and scope. The goal of the LCA study guides the preceding steps. With the goal in mind, a functional unit and a system boundary are selected. The functional unit is generally the function of the product or service of interest, for which the study is essentially initiated. The functional unit enables the definition of reference flow, on the basis of which all other input and output amounts of the product system can be quantified. Furthermore, a system boundary is needed in order to define the borders of the product system.

Similar to this, a goal, the material and product flows and the scope need to be defined within the novel SAF and for the system dynamics model. The SAF is designed to allow for a sustainability assessment on a regional scale, meaning that the impact measured with the sustainability indicators reference to an entire region. This can also be done with LCA and has also been used for measuring impacts on a company level (e.g. corporate carbon footprint) with a reference value for a specific timeframe, e.g. for one year. The advantage of the system dynamics model is that the change of the values can be considered and simulated over time with the simultaneous consideration of the regional context and market. Market and context constraints of a region limit the change of the values, which allows one to conduct a scenario analysis to find out which solution or change suits the region the most. This overcomes a limitation of LCAs, as the recommendations resulting from an LCA study are rarely measured against the context in which their implementation should occur, thereby limiting the feasibility of these recommendations.

5.1.1 Defining the goal

The goal of a sustainability assessment using the SD model acts as the basis for further defining the studied material and production flow types as well as the scope of the analysis. In essence, the goal describes the reason for carrying out the assessment. Following the goal of the TREASoURcE project and thus the purpose of this novel approach, the described goal should include the following:

- In general, what materials and products are relevant? (1)
- What circular economy strategy is pursued? (2)
- What areas of protection are relevant? (3)
- Who is the target audience? (4)

This information shall be available within a concisely defined goal for the sustainability assessment. Some elements can nevertheless be indirectly referenced. An example for a defined goal can be:

„The goal is to assess the introduction of an e-market place and a rural-urban symbiosis tool (2) in terms of its impact on biodiversity (3). The tools aim to increase the availability of bio-based side and waste streams for the production of biogas and biofertilizers (1). Assessment results will act as decision-making support for policymakers (4).

From this goal one can derive the material and products (bio-based side and waste streams to biogas and biofertilizers), the circular economy strategies (an e-market place and a rural-urban symbiosis tool), the area of protection (biodiversity) and the main target audience (policymakers). As this may seem in some ways limited, e.g. by the fact that not only policymakers will be relevant stakeholders or that other impact categories may also be relevant and are linked to the main one here, further details need to be defined in the scope.

There are several preceding steps that come after the initial definition of the goal. These are further specifications linked to the aspects defined in the goal, such as a clearer definition of the geographical boundaries or the complete list of linked sustainability indicators. It is important to note that the initially defined goal is by no means the final definition of the goal, as several insights gain in later stages of the assessment might necessitate a revision of the initial definition.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.1

- A goal that indicates materials and products, the circular economy strategy, areas of protection, and the target audience is defined.

5.1.2 Types of materials and products

One main advantage of the system dynamics model is that it is very flexible, allowing the modeller to decide on the scope and expanse of the assessment. It is for one possible to assess multiple flows that occur in parallel or in some cases merge and become new flows. This means the modeller can decide on what types of flows and how many flows to include. This again will be closely linked to the goal of the study and is especially relevant for regional-scale assessments.

In system dynamics it possible to work with so called arrays (see Figure 6). This allows for a system dynamics model to be multi-dimensional. When defining the links between the elements of the system dynamics model, formulas can refer to specific elements of an array. That way e.g. the impact calculations for a specific product (one single dimension) is exclusive for that single product. The number of dimensions or elements within an array is theoretically not limited. Yet, with an increasing number of dimensions one is faced with an exponential increase of data requirements. Thus, it might be useful to consider whether the inclusion of certain products is necessary. One product might represent entire markets. Such “indicator products” make the assessment more viable in terms of data collection.

Figure 6: Arrays of the stock “Products in use” representing different plastic materials

The main types of materials and products can be derived for the defined goal. Continuing on the previously mentioned example, this would mean that biogas and biofertilizers are the main products of interest and the bio-based side and waste streams the main input materials. This can be extended, by e.g. also including competing or conventional products, such as natural gas and fossil-based fertilizers, thereby allowing a consequential impact assessment, or primary input materials that are not covered by bio-based side and waste streams.

When thinking about this example for a region, it becomes apparent that multiple flows need to be considered. A region might have different agricultural sectors that produce by-products that could be used to produce biogas. Crops such as maize or barley might produce these. Different factors, such as abundance in the region or suitability for biogas production, may redeem whether such crops are relevant for the purpose of e.g. biogas production. These factors need to be considered and may lead to a revision of the flows throughout different phases of the assessment.

Expanding on that, revision will also occur with the definition of the geographical and system boundaries. Geographical boundaries will determine availability of certain flows within a region whereas system boundaries will determine the value chain structure and thus the inclusion of flows. To conclude this with the example at hand, maize and barley by products are selected as input materials and biogas is selected as the final product. In addition, natural gas is also considered to be able to observe the

market and impact shifts with the introduction of additional biogas. This essentially also supports the definition of the system boundaries.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.2

- Materials and products are defined for all value chain stages that are considered based on the system boundaries.
- Materials and products are revised and reviewed based on findings throughout the assessment.

5.1.3 Value chain system boundaries

At this point the modeller determines the product life cycle stages that are taken into consideration during the assessment. This shall be done for each product. The core module of the system dynamics model is already made up of general life cycle stages (e.g. “Products in use”, “End-of-Life”, “Recycling” etc.).

The production stock represents the entire upstream supply chain of the product, meaning everything before the product is offered on the market. The products offered are those that are in stock on the market and are available for purchase. Once the product is purchase, it enters the use phase. Depending on the product lifetime, the product might stay in this stock for a longer or shorter period of time. At some point it reaches the end-of-life stage, where it is either littered, disposed or cycled back into production supply chains. If it is cycled, the material or product either enters re-use, recycling or regeneration.

It is important to define the system boundaries for system dynamics model, but also for the LCSA and MFA. For the system dynamics model this determines the pathway for each product within the general core value chain structure. Whether e.g. disposal is considered, or reuse is a relevant pathway. The system boundaries for the supporting tools, such as LCSA, define the “hidden” supply chains for certain products. This is especially relevant for the determination of impact factor for the sustainability indicators. When e.g. biogas is set against natural gas, it will be necessary to include the supply chain of the imported natural gas. This will show the potential benefits and avoided impacts of substituting certain products.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.3

- System boundaries are defined for the value chains studied.
- These boundaries are continuously updated based on findings throughout the assessment.

5.1.4 Regional boundaries

As previously stated, the goal of the SAF to find a suitable sustainability strategy for the assessed region. Selecting the regional boundaries will thus define the context of the value chain. Context

indicators are important to consider, as this will essentially give insight into the success factors and limitations of certain strategies and essentially allows for a more effective implementation.

The regional boundaries shall have physical geographical boundaries and can e.g. be cities or municipalities. It might also be useful to consider regions that are also within administrative division. This will make it easier to define the policy environment of the value chains. The geographical boundaries will determine what materials and products come from outside and which one leave the boundaries. In other words, these flows are imported or exported. Some of the products will come from outside the regional boundaries and some waste flows will leave the boundaries to be processed elsewhere.

Setting the regional boundaries is also linked closely to the determined value chain structure. During data collection it might occur that certain supply chains are not in place in specific regions. This might require the assessed materials and products to be reviewed or even the assessed value chain stages. Some regions e.g. might have higher availability of bio-based side and waste streams than others, making these for suitable for biogas plants.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.4

- Regional boundaries are selected for the assessment.

5.1.5 Timeframe

Defining a timeframe is especially relevant for the simulation of the system dynamics model. Results are recalculated at each time step with the changing parameter values. The x-axis of the resulting graphs represents the timescale. For running the calculations, the time unit as well as the amount of time shall be defined. It is important that this is in line with the goal of the assessment. This might especially relevant when considering the impact of certain circular economy strategies. Some strategies may only be redeemed as impactful a few years after implementation.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.5

- A realistic timeframe for the results calculation is defined.
- The timeframe is continuously reviewed and revised based on findings throughout the assessment.

5.1.6 Indicator types and metrics

The indicators are arranged into different indicator types, including impact indicators for sustainability, in a social, environmental and economic dimension, performance indicators for circularity, context indicators, as well as market indicators. The modeller decides which indicators are relevant for the assessment. To a certain extent, this can be derived from the goal of the assessment. In the end, the selected indicators will depend on criteria such as relevance, data availability, accuracy and consensus.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.6

- Sustainability (social, environmental and economic) indicators are selected
- Circularity indicators are selected.
- Context and market indicators are selected.

5.1.7 Data requirements and assumptions

The SD model, as well as other assessment approaches of the SAF, requires data inputs. The data requirements can be derived from the model structure as well as the geographic and value chain boundaries. The first step here should be to list the datasets that are needed. The data collection phase is commenced with the initial list of data requirements. Data collection is conducted with a data collection template. In the data collection template, the datasets are categorized into the different modules of the SD model.

The SD model works with quantified data. This means that all qualitative observations (e.g. for certain market indicators) need to be scaled and then linked to elements in the model with appropriately defined relationships. Data sources will vary according to the data collection tools used. Some data sets will require pre-calculations before being inserted into the system dynamics model. This especially goes for the impact factors calculated using LCA tools. Further data sources can include literature sources, statistic banks, government data, data collected with surveys and interviews or measured data using measurement instruments. Primary and measured data shall always be prioritized and are positively recognized in terms of data quality.

In order to conduct prospective modelling, the modeller shall consider that several data points with change over time or during the upscaling of a technology. The value thus needs to be defined for each time step within the simulation time scale. First, the elements of the model that change over time or with upscaling need to be identified. Second, approaches for determining the developments (how the values change over time) need to be chosen and applied. Approaches include but are not limited to: assumption, socioeconomic pathways, electricity transition pathways, historical trends, technological trends, etc.

During data collection, the modeller is likely to face data gaps. For some missing data, further calculations can be used to derive required data. As the assessment framework focuses on regions, it might be hard to find data for those specific regions. Often though the data is available on other geographic scales, such as the national or global level. With this, the modeller can apply allocation methods to come up with the data for the region. For example, a population-based allocation approach would scale down the planetary boundaries to an individual and then assign those boundaries to a region based on the population living in that region. Nevertheless, the actual value, determined by e.g. the economic importance, of the products assessed also needs to be considered and determined to what extent boundaries are assigned to regions. These calculations and the linked method shall be described in more detail by the modeller in the results report.

A further approach for dealing with data gaps is by using qualitative assumptions. These can for example be expert-based or strategy-based. There are several integrated validation steps in the

framework to ensure that the assumptions do not deviate entirely from reality. The SAF requires e.g. a minimum model structure that ensures the inclusion of essential model elements. Also, ranges are defined for certain datasets as modelling can only occur under specifically defined limits. Those go e.g. for the population, as it is outside of realistic limits when the population quickly goes down to 0. The validation approaches described below also ensure a certain degree of validity for the assumptions made. Here, the modeller shall e.g. compare the simulated results with historical trends or conduct several model stability tests to see whether the results are reliable.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.7

- An initial list of data points is developed.
- For each of the data sets, data sources and data collection strategies are pre-defined.
- A strategy for dealing with data gaps is defined.
- The data collection method is continuously revised and reviewed based on assessment findings.

5.1.8 Model structure adjustments

The elements constituting the structure of the SD model can be categorized as essential and non-essential, based on the necessity of their inclusion in the model for its correct functioning.

The essential elements constitute the minimal structure necessary to capture the dynamics of the system being modelled. Therefore, the elements identified hereby as essential, i.e., comprising the minimum structure of the SD model, should always be included in the structure of the SD model. This minimum structure provides an SD model foundation that can be adjusted according to the specific goals and scope of the assessment.

The following elements/modules of the SD model are defined as comprising the minimum structure of the SD model:

- **Market Module:**

The market module is a crucial component of the system dynamics model and the link between the demand and supply through price is essential. This linkage is vital for accurately representing market dynamics, ensuring the model reflects real-world economic interactions. However, for preliminary screening purposes, demand and price can be treated as exogenous variables, simplifying the model without significantly compromising its integrity. In this case, the market module can be simplified to be modelled by *price_trends*, *demand_trends* and *non_eq_desired_product_stock* variables. Including these variables ensures that the model remains responsive to broader economic trends, which can have significant impacts on the market. Moreover, the inclusion of the *reuse_appreciation* and *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* elements in the model is fundamental when modelling the transition to circular value chains.

- **System Constraints:**

The model should include production capacity, resources, and desired production to reflect the system's operational limits. Production capacity represents the maximum output based on available resources and technology.

- **Main Value Chain Activities:**

Activities related to the production of primary products and the circular value chain must be included to capture the essential processes and interactions within the system. These activities are central to the model, ensuring it reflects the critical elements of the value chain that influence sustainability and circularity outcomes.

- **Indicators**

The sustainability assessment indicators do not influence the dynamics of the system under study and can be adjusted as needed. However, it is necessary to include at least one sustainability indicator to obtain at least some information on the performance of the system in terms of its sustainability.

Building on the minimum structure of the model, it is expected to be suitable to adjust the generic SD model presented in this SAF to suit the specific assessment requirements better. The adjustments can be done in accordance with individual parts of the *Goal & Scope definition phase*. The following aspects can be considered when adjusting the model structure:

- **Goal**

Depending on the desired granularity, results can be aggregated to provide a single system-level impact value per category or disaggregated to show impacts associated with individual products or value chains.

- **System Boundaries**

Certain value chain activities and material flows might be excluded to simplify the model. , For instance, the value chain activities related to product utilization in other systems might be excluded if such utilization is not relevant to the assessed value chain. Similarly,

- **Circular Strategies**

The inclusion or exclusion of the circular material/product flows depends on the circular strategy being assessed. For example, recycling product flow might be essential in a model assessing recycling impacts but the reuse product flow could be irrelevant.

- **Indicators**

Specific indicators can be added or removed based on their relevance to the assessment goals. For instance, if the goal of the assessment is to assess the carbon footprint, only the global warming potential indicator can be assessed.

- **Material Flows/Treatment Pathways**

The arrays used in the arrayed stocks and flows can be adjusted to match the scope of the assessment. For example, only one recycling pathway can be considered if there is no evidence for other recycling technologies in the assessed system.

- **Scenarios**

The model structure should be adapted to reflect different scenarios. For example, in a scenario with minimum recycled content requirements for plastic products, the model should reflect inelastic demand in the market module. Similarly, new model structures can be developed to better represent regulatory environments or other scenario-specific factors.

In the case of ECOPT2 model, the parameters that should be adjusted to align with the goal and scope of the assessment are related to the system constraints. The main two constraints-related parameters for adjustment would be the *willingness to adopt* and possible inclusion or exclusion of the flows corresponding to the import or export of the products into the assessed system.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.8

The minimum structure of the SD model is defined as being comprised of the following elements/modules:

- Market module
- System constraints
- Main value chain activities
- Indicators

While the minimum structure of the SD model should be always retained, adjustments to the other elements of the SD model can be suitable. The possible adjustment can be based on the individual steps of the goal & scope definition phase of the framework such as goal, system boundaries, strategies, scenarios or materials and products assessed in the assessment.

5.1.9 Circular economy strategies and scenarios

The SAF assessments aims to identify hotspots, patterns, risks, and chances for the circular economy solutions of the TREASoURcE project. This especially allows to identify solutions that are suitable from a sustainability perspective. Essentially it comes down to finding the “best” circular economy strategy. What this strategy looks like shall be defined by the modeller within the goal and scope definition phase of the assessment. This takes on several stages that are described here.

To assess and prioritize the most suitable strategy involves looking at several alternatives and ultimately deciding on one or several alternatives on basis of one or several indicators. This decision-making process will commonly require several calculation iterations, with each iteration calculated with a specific set of values for the parameters in the SD model. These parameter sets shall represent “what if” scenarios. Findings from each iteration shall support the definition of the parameter set for the next iteration. If the selected circular economy strategy does not have a significant effect, such a strategy might not be desirable. For further analysis, it might come down to finding the scenario and adjusting the model in such a way that prevents a negative development from occurring. In the final phase of the assessment, the modeller shall interpret the different developments for each strategy

alternative and decide on the most suitable option depending on the desired outcome and considering the trade-offs.

The strategies of interest can be derived from the goal that has been previously defined. Circular economy strategies can be generally characterized as shown in Table 2 (Ibanez-Fores et al., 2023):

Table 2: Circular economy strategies and strategy types.

Strategy	Strategy types
Design	Design for disassembly
	Design for durability
	Design for repair
	Design for recycling
	Design for resource efficiency
Materials	Low impact materials
	Abundant/renewable materials
	Local production
	Recycled materials
	Recyclable materials
Production	Industrial symbiosis
	Energy and material efficiency
	Circular production
	Product passport, tracking
Output	Incentivize return
	Re-Use
	Refurbishment and upgrade
	Recycling
	Energy recovery
	Composting, regeneration
	Maintenance or repair
	Infrastructure
	Resource and energy efficiency during use
	Collection and sorting possibilities
Collaboration	Sharing platforms
	Product service platforms
Communication	Product labelling
	Digital information

Within these general strategy types, the specification of the strategy might differ depending on the actor that aims to implement the strategy. Business, governments or consumers might all have different specified strategies with the same general strategy type. By looking again at the earlier example, the more specific strategy is to introduce an e-market platform as well as a rural-urban symbiosis tool.

This touches on several general circular economy strategies, such as industrial symbiosis, product service platforms, but also composting and regeneration.

Linking the more specific innovations to general circular economy strategies allows one to, for one, identify the relevant parameters in the SD model, but also to have an overarching strategy for a range of several more specific alternatives. This range can be pre-defined based on scenario development approaches, such as:

- Opportunity-based: looking at current developments and identifying opportunities
- Target-based: Setting explicit targets and linking these targets to limits
- Policy-based: selecting scenarios based on policies and policy trends (Woltjer et al. 2018)

Once the strategies are linked to a list of alternative scenarios that shall be considered in the assessment, the changes that occur when pursuing these different strategies shall be identified. For the SD model, this means defining the elements and parameters of the model that change when actions within a strategy are implemented. How these parameters change will be defined in an iterative manner during the SD modelling phase.

When implementing e.g. an e-market platform to enable the use of bio-based side and waste streams for the production of biogas and biofertilizers, a better distribution of biomass to biogas and biofertilizer production sites might be observed. This improved distribution e.g. changes the production amounts for the products that use the bio-based input materials. For the analysis of the different strategy alternatives, the values for the relevant parameters in the SD model need to be adjusted in order to represent this development.

Summary of SAF requirements for 1.9

All in all, selecting the strategies shall be done in the following steps:

1. Define the strategy options based on the sustainability assessment goal
2. Link these options to an overarching circular economy strategy
3. Define several alternatives / scenarios for each strategy option
4. For each of the alternatives, define what parameters in the system dynamics model need to be adjusted
5. With the system dynamics modelling step, define how the parameters change

5.2 Phase 2: Data collection

As mentioned, the extent of the data requirements depends on the previously defined goal & scope. The types of data were already described in section 5.1.7. Depending on the type of data, different data collection tools may be necessary. As the final results are calculated with the SD model, the data is first centrally collected in a data collection table. An excel template was developed for this, as shown in Figure 7.

Data collection template for the TREASOURcE sustainability assessment framework

Guidance:
 The sustainability assessment framework developed in the TREASOURcE project and applies system dynamics to assess the sustainability of circular economy solutions on a regional scale. To provide insights into the feasibility of the solutions, a multi-indicator approach is used, considering sustainability indicators (economic, environmental, social) as well as market and current indicators. With the data provided in this data collection template, the development of these indicators can be simulated over time. Several aspects need to be defined for the scope of the assessment:
 1. Time interval (e.g. year, month, day) for evaluation
 2. System boundaries (regional boundaries)
 3. Types of material and product flows

Overview of system and scope:

Enter initial values data

Parameters	Dimension	Value	Unit	Description/assumption	Comment	Data source
Products offered (initial value)						
HDPE	t		tonnes			
LDPE	t		tonnes			
PS	t		tonnes			
PP	t		tonnes			
PVC	t		tonnes			
PET	t		tonnes			
recycled HDPE	t		tonnes			
recycled LDPE	t		tonnes			
recycled PS	t		tonnes			
recycled PP	t		tonnes			
recycled PVC	t		tonnes			
recycled PET	t		tonnes			
Purchased products (initial value)						
HDPE	t		tonnes			
LDPE	t		tonnes			
PS	t		tonnes			
PP	t		tonnes			
PVC	t		tonnes			
PET	t		tonnes			
recycled HDPE	t		tonnes			
recycled LDPE	t		tonnes			
recycled PS	t		tonnes			
recycled PP	t		tonnes			
recycled PVC	t		tonnes			
recycled PET	t		tonnes			
Products in use (initial value)						
HDPE	5659,763139	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
LDPE	6275,064219	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
PS	5803,119419	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
PP	6783,507077	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
PVC	14609,68054	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
PET	1577,204689	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
recycled HDPE	1479,675245	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
recycled LDPE	1826,137086	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.
recycled PS	1687,169639	tonnes	tonnes	const. regional stock for products in use		NFA model/own exp.

Figure 7: Data collection template

In the system dynamics model, the data is inputted either manually or using an excel sheet with a suitable structure and format. By selecting the relevant stocks, converters or flows, the modeller is able to input the data in cells or tables. The data input interface for the SD model is displayed in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Data input option in the system dynamics model

Some data might need to be pre-calculated. This is especially relevant for e.g. for the impact factors from the LCSA tools. In such cases, inventory data is initially required, for the inputs and outputs of the processes in the relevant value chains. Selected life cycle impact assessment methods can then be used to calculate the impacts per unit of product or output. The data entry related to the environmental impact factors used in the SD model is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Data input option for impact factors in the system dynamics model

Once all data has been collected, the modeller can continue on to calculate the results. In some cases, the results initially calculated may lead to unexpected results. The modeller should at this point review the linked data and consider whether either model structure adjustments need to be made or the collected data needs to be revised.

Summary of SAF requirements for the phase 2

- Primary and secondary data is collected for the relevant variables, parameters, and indicators.
- MFA is used to collect material flow data.
- LCSA results are calculated
- All data is collected in a data collection template and transferred into the system dynamics model.
- Data is updated based on revisions and reviews.

5.3 Phase 3: Results calculation

In this phase, the tools developed within the SAF are populated with the data collected in the previous step and results are calculated. The SAF involves several approaches that assess various aspects of the system and its material flows and sustainability. The approaches and the results obtained from them are presented below:

- **System dynamics:** Results of the future behaviour of the whole system under assessment, including the corresponding sustainability and circularity indicators. These results form the foundation of the sustainability and circularity assessment of this framework.
- **Prospective LCSA:** Results of the sustainability indicators related to individual value chain activities, predicted according to the modelled future development. These results are used as an input into the SD model.

- **MFA:** Results on the material flows (and stocks) corresponding to the assessed system. These results are used as an input to the SD model.
- **Dynamic MFA:** Results on the material flows (and stocks) that reflect certain dynamics of the assessed system. These results are used for a more granular analysis of material flows of the system (compared with the SD model) and are used for the validation of the material flows calculated by the SD model.
- **ECOPT2:** Results on the optimal circular transition pathway for the assessed value chains based on the objective of specific impacts minimisation. These results are used in addition to the SD model results and also for the validation of the results of the SD model.

The process of results calculation is generally comprised of three parts: applying the tools to calculate the results, validating the results (also through the validation of the tools), and scoring the results. These three steps are described in the following sections.

5.3.1 Applying tools

The results are mainly calculated in the SD model. MFA and dynamic MFA are used to provide data for and validate results of the system dynamics model. LCSA and prospective LCSA are used to calculate impact factors of the area of protection, including social, environmental and economic impact indicators. For this, the software openLCA¹ will be used. LCSA and MFA are established methods for which established tools are available. Therefore, these approaches will not be further elaborated here. This section will focus on the SD modelling, which is a new approach for sustainability assessments.

5.3.1.1 System dynamics modelling

Application of the SD modelling approach in the SAF involves the following steps:

- Development of the structure of the SD model
- Populating the SD model with data
- Running the simulation and extracting the results

These three steps are described in more detail in the following subsections.

5.3.1.1.1 Development of the structure of the SD model

In this step, the development of the SD model is carried out according to the qualitative specifications of the modelled system. The development of the SD model was performed by using the *Stella Architect* software, as it suited the needs of the expected model structure (e.g., allowing arrayed elements) in the best way.

¹ [Introduction - openLCA 2 manual \(greendelta.github.io\)](https://github.com/greendelta/openLCA2-manual)
Funded by the European Union

The model combines two main approaches relevant for the assessment of sustainability of systems: life cycle thinking and SD. Life cycle modelling is used primarily to represent the value chain activities and their associated impacts, as they occur within the system under assessment. The impacts considered in the LCA model represent the sustainability of the system comprehensively, relating to environmental, social and economic indicators. On the other hand, the SD modelling is used to define rules for the interaction between the different elements of the system and simulate the change of these elements over time. The model also has market and context indicators as well as circularity aspects integrated. The SD model can be structured into six main modules, as described in Table 3. The individual modules are composed by the stocks, flows and variables, which are interconnected by the mathematical relationships defined between them. The overview of all SD model elements, along with their definition and a brief explanation can be found in Table 5 of Annex I.

Table 3: Overview of the main modules of the developed system dynamics model.

System module	Description
Value chain	Represents the activities occurring within the assessed value chains. The value chains are generally modelled from the raw material extraction stage until the end-of-life treatment, including the circular end-of-life treatment pathways.
Market and context	Represents the market, i.e., price, demand, and supply developments (and their interaction). Additionally, the context indicators (e.g., population of the region) specific to the assessed case are integrated to influence the market.
Resources	Represents the renewable and non-renewable resources available for the assessed value chain.
Social impacts	Represents the social sustainability impacts associated with the system.
Environmental impacts	Represents the environmental impacts associated with the system.
Costs and value added	Represents monetary flows between individual value chain activities, i.e., costs and economic value created.

Value chain module

The value chain module of the model represents activities linked together within the assessed value chain. The value chain module, as incorporated in the SD model developed in Stella, is presented in Figure 10. The module incorporates all life cycle activities associated with the products that create value within the assessed value chains. The products and materials selected to represent the value chain are defined in the scoping phase of the assessment based on stakeholder inputs (see more in 5.1.2). It is important to note here that the SD model considers several material/product flows at the same time within a single simulation. These materials/products might interact and influence each other. All life cycle activities associated with the products that represent the assessed value chain are included in the module. The activities that have an indirect link to the assessed value chain are incorporated in the module as per the scope definition.

For instance, in the case of *circular plastics* value chain, a set of polymers (PET, PVC, LDPE, HDPE, PP and mixed plastics) could be selected to represent the value chain. In addition, the activities with an indirect link to the value chain could be included in the model, e.g., the avoided recycling of the plastics in the regions outside of the assessed system could be included in the assessment.

Figure 10: Overview of the value chain module of the developed SD model, the black flows and stocks refer to the key value chain modelled; the pink arrows between the elements of the model indicate which elements are used as parameters in the definition of other elements.

As shown in Figure 10, the key value chain model is composed of 6 stocks (Products offered, Purchased products, Products in use, Products at EoL, Reuse feedstock, Recycling/biorecovery feedstock). These stocks are connected to each other through flows, which correspond to individual key value chain activities.

The value chain module starts with the production submodule, as displayed in Figure 11. The primary production is modelled by a flow called “*production*”, which is defined as follows:

$$MIN(capacity_rate_to_demand[product];resources_to_demand[product])$$

Hence, the primary production is equal to the minimum of two variables (*capacity_rate_to_demand* and *resources_to_demand*), which are also a minimum-searching functions (between the production

demand and production capacity or available resources, respectively). Consequently, the primary production is determined as a minimum function, which considers three parameters: available resources, desired production (from the supplier's side) and production capacity.

Figure 11: Production submodule of the SD model.

Additionally, in the case of primary production side streams, the production quantity is not determined by the minimising function of demand, resources and capacity. Rather, it is defined as being equal to the production of a primary product multiplied by a *production_sidestream_ratio* specific to each side-stream and primary product.

The produced primary products (and sidestreams) flow to the *Products_offered* stock, which represents the market offer of the defined products within the defined region. The trade between different regions is considered as well, as products can be both imported (added to the *Products_offered* stock) and exported (taken from *Products_offered* stock) to the regional market. The import and export rates of products are determined exogenously by the variables of the *production_import_rate* and *production_export_rate* variables.

The *Products_offered* stock is depleted by the *sale* flow, i.e., the products that are offered on the market are taken from the market by going through the sale process. The *sale* flow is also defined as a minimum-searching function. It is limited by two factors: demand (*demand* stock) and supply (*Products_offered* stock). The sold products are transferred to the *Purchased_products* stock, as shown in

Figure 12. The *Purchased_products* stock can be depleted through 3 outflow channels. Firstly, it can be utilized in other system outside the scope of the assessment, corresponding to the *indirect_utilization* flow. Secondly, it can be utilized within the assessed system, corresponding to the *Direct_utilization* flow. Thirdly, it can be not utilized within the assessed system but still go through a waste treatment process within the assessed system, corresponding to the *unutilized_wastage/transport_of_sidestreams_for_recovery* flow. This option applies to the products that get purchased but are wasted without being utilized, e.g., food that is purchased but is thrown away rather than consumed. Additionally, this flow is relevant also for the transfer of the purchased sidestreams to the recovery processing. The rates of the *Indirect_utilization*, *Direct_utilization* and *unutilized_wastage/transport_of_sidestreams_for_recovery* flows are determined by variables based on exogenous data input. The *Direct_utilization* flow transfers the products to the *Products_in_use* stock, which represents the amount of the specified products/materials that are in use within the assessed system.

It is important to note that the *unutilized_wastage/transport_of_sidestreams_for_recovery* flow classifies the products into individual end-of-life classes based on the treatment pathways that is utilized. The structure of the classification into these end-of-life classes is explained in the following paragraphs.

Figure 12: Sales and utilization submodule of the SD model.

The *Products_in_use* stock gets depleted by the *product_decay* flow, which leads to the *Products_at_EoL* stock, as shown in Figure 13. This flow represents the products that reach their end of life once they are no longer usable. The *product_decay* flow is defined by the *EoL-classified_product_death* variable, which defines the quantities of the product that reach their end of life and classifies each of the modelled products into the classes of the end-of-life treatment (called “EoL class” in the model). In the model, 10 different EoL classes are established:

- Disposal

- Litter
- Recycling/biorecovery 1
- Recycling/biorecovery 2
- Recycling/biorecovery 3
- Recycling/biorecovery 4
- Reuse 1
- Reuse 2
- Reuse 3
- Composting

The recycling/biorecovery and reuse treatment is modelled to be carried out via several pathways, which are specific to the recycling/biorecovery and reuse technology used. More specifically, the generic SD model features 4 treatment pathways for recycling/biorecovery and 3 pathways for reuse. The amounts coming to the individual EoL classes are defined based on the variables corresponding to the individual EoL class rates (*reuse_rate*, *recycling/biorecovery_rate*, *litter_rate*, *composting_rate* and *disposal_rate*). The *EoL_classes* variable determines the relative contributions of the individual recycling/biorecovery and reuse classes to the total amount of products that get recycled/biorecovered and reused. These rates are defined exogenously by the user. The *EoL-classified_product_death* variable is defined by multiplying the individual EoL-class-related rates by the *product_death* variable, which equals the total amount of individual products reaching their end of life. The definitions of the *EoL-classified_product_death* differ among individual EoL classes based on whether there are more treatment pathways possible within one EoL treatment approach, as you can see on the following examples:

$$disposal_rate[product]*product_death[product]$$

$$"recycling/biorecovery_rate"[product]*EoL_classes["Recycling/biorecovery_1";product]*product_death[product]$$

The *product_death* variable is defined based on the average product lifespan (*product_lifespan* variable) and the inflow to the *Products_in_use* stock (which corresponds to the *Direct_utilization* flow), utilizing the DELAY function. However, to model the product death before the product lifespan is reached by the simulation time, a variable *product_death_rate* is used, modelling the product death linearly, as a fraction of the *Products_in_use* stock. The equation defining the *product_death* variable follows below:

$$IF (TIME \leq product_lifespan)$$

THEN

$$initial_product_death_rate*INIT(Products_in_use)$$

ELSE

$$DELAY(Direct_utilization; product_lifespan)$$

Figure 13: Product decay submodule of the SD model.

The *Products_at_EoL* stock is fed by two inflows (*product_decay* and *unutilized_waste/transport_of_sidestreams_for_recovery* flows). The stock, as presented in Figure 14, is depleted by six outflows:

- *Composting*
- *EoL_export*
- *Disposal*
- *Littering*
- *Collection_for_recycling/biorecovery*
- *Collection_for_reuse*

Figure 14: End-of-life treatment submodule of the SD model.

The modelling of all outflows follows the same logic. The products flows categorized into individual EoL classes that are fed to the stock are divided between the EoL treatment within the assessed system and treatment outside of the system (represented by the *EoL_export* flow). Hence, the outflows corresponding to the EoL treatment are defined in the following way (the example of disposal applies to all other EoL classes as well):

$$Products_at_EoL[Disposal;Products]-EoL_export[Disposal;Products]$$

The *EoL_export outflow* that represents the export of the EoL products outside of the system is defined using a user-input *EoL_export_rate* values:

$$Products_at_EoL * EoL_export_rate$$

The value chain module includes two circular EoL treatment channels, reuse and recycling/biorecovery. The recycling/biorecovery channel refers to either the recycling of a specified product (e.g., plastic being recycled) or the recovery of valuable products from biobased side and waste streams. Both reuse and recycling/biorecovery pathways follow the same value chain activity sequence and are modelled analogously. They are represented by the following activity sequence: *collection* flow → *feedstock* stock → *transformation* flow → *Products_offered* stock.

The value chain of the recycling/biorecovery circular pathway is presented in Figure 15. The *Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock* is modelled assuming that the product/materials collected at their end-of-life are all aggregated into one EoL class. The stock is fed by two inflows: *collection_for_recycling/biorecovery* and *additive_materials_for_recycling/biorecovery*. The *additive_materials_for_recycling/biorecovery* flow represents the additional materials that are needed to be added to the collected EoL products/materials during the recycling/biorecovery processes. The *additive_materials_for_recycling/biorecovery* flow is determined based on a linear equation, utilizing the "*recycling/biorecovery_additives_ratio*" variable defined by the user:

$$SUM("collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[EoL_Class; *]) * "recycling/biorecovery_additives_ratio"$$

Figure 15: Recycling/biorecovery submodule of the SD model.

The *Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock* is depleted by two flows: *recycling/biorecovery_loss* and *recycling/biorecovery_transformation*. The *recycling/biorecovery_loss* flow accounts for the losses occurring during the recycling or biorecovery processes and the main function of this flow is to maintain the mass balance of the *Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock* stock. It is determined as a linear function of the *recycling/biorecovery_transformation* flow and the *recycling_loss_ratio* variable, defined as follows:

$$recycling_loss_ratio * SUM("recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[EoL_Class; *])$$

The *recycling_loss_ratio* is defined in relation to the throughput of the *recycling/biorecovery_transformation*. Hence, in a process where 50% of the feedstock material is lost, the *recycling_loss_ratio* would be equal to 1. The relationship between the recycling loss (i.e., the percentage of the feedstock lost during the recycling) and the *recycling_loss_ratio* can be expressed as:

$$Recycling\ loss = 1 - 1 / (1 + recycling_loss_ratio)$$

The *recycling/biorecovery_transformation* flow represents either the process of recycling of the feedstock material into new products (primarily in a closed loop) or the recovery of valuable products from organic feedstocks (e.g., recovery of biogas from agricultural sidestreams). The logic behind the

modelling of this flow corresponds to the approach taken for the modelling of the primary products. That is, the magnitude of the flow is defined by a minimum-searching function, which considers three limiting factors: resources, processing capacity and the desired production of the secondary products (reflecting the supply desired by the suppliers). However, in contrast to the production of primary products, the resources limiting the production are not only renewable and non-renewable raw materials available to the value chain but also the feedstock of end-of-life materials/products (represented by the *Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock* stock in the SD model). Moreover, the *Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock* stock is partitioned only according to the individual *EoL class* dimension, while the *recycling/biorecovery_transformation* flow is partitioned into both the *EoL class* and *Products* dimensions. Hence, a *Recycling_feedstock_mapping_factor* variable is used to partition the feedstock in the individual *EoL classes* among the individual classes in the *Products* dimension. For instance, 35% of the feedstock available in the *EoL class* “Chemical recycling 1” of the *Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock* stock can be mapped to be used for the recycling of the “LDPE” class of the *Products* dimension. In this case, the *Recycling_feedstock_mapping_factor* of the dimensions [“Chemical recycling 1”; “LDPE”] would be equal to 0.35. When defining this variable, it is important to ensure that the total sum over a single *EoL class* does not exceed 1. Considering these provisions, the formula for the *recycling/biorecovery_transformation* is as follows:

$$\text{MIN}(\text{"recycling/biorecovery_capacity"}[\text{EoL_Class};\text{Products}]; \text{recycling_resources_to_demand}[\text{EoL_Class};\text{Products}])$$

The value chain corresponding to the reuse of the products is modelled in a way identical to the recycling/biorecovery, with the *reuse_transformation* flow depleting the *reuse_feedstock* stock and making use of all the analogous variables defined for reuse.

Market module

The market module has an essential position in the SD model, as it drives and regulates both the production of primary materials and products and the production of circular materials and products. The whole market module is depicted in Figure 16. The market module generally looks at the dynamics of demand, supply and price and the interaction among them. In general, the module is conceptualised as being composed of three types of elements, the non-equilibrium elements, the equilibrium elements and the context elements.

Figure 16: Overview of the market module in the SD model.

The equilibrium elements of the module represent a tendency of the system to move towards equilibrium between supply and demand by reaching an equilibrium price. This is incorporated in the model by calculating the change in price that would be necessary for demand and supply to become equal (represented by the *change_in_equilibrium_price* variable of the module). The *change_in_equilibrium_price* variable is defined based on the demand (*demand* stock), supply (*Products_offered* stock), their elasticities of price (Price elasticity of supply being represented by the *supply_elasticity* variable and the price rate elasticity of demand being represented by the *demand_elasticity* variable), and price (*Price* stock). The relationship between these parameters (defining the *change_in_equilibrium_price*) is formulated as follows:

$$(demand - Products_offered) * Price / (supply_elasticity * (Products_offered) - demand_elasticity * demand)$$

The price change needed to reach the equilibrium is then affecting the *Price* stock via the *Price equilibration* flow. This extent of the effect that the *change_in_equilibrium_price* variable exhibits on the *Price* stock via this flow is determined by the *Equilibration_factor* variable. This variable is used to determine the extent to which the equilibration between the regional supply and demand influences the price and can generally range between 0 and 1.

As the market tends to reach equilibrium, the change in *Price* influences the supply and demand. In the case of supply, the variable affected is the *Desired_production* variable in the case of primary

products². It is important to note here that the *Desired_production* variable is influenced by both equilibrium and non-equilibrium elements of the market module. Hence, both of these elements are used in its equation to define it. The form of the equation was determined based on how price elasticity of supply is defined in the economic theory. The equilibrium elements pertaining to the change of the *Desired_production* due to the price change are highlighted in green in the *Desired_production* formula presented below:

$$\text{"non-eq_desired_product_stock"[PRODUCT_1]} * (1 - \text{"recycling/biorecovery_appreciation"[PRODUCT_1]}) * (1 - \text{"reuse_appreciation"[PRODUCT_1]}) + \text{Products_offered[PRODUCT_1]} * \text{supply_elasticity[PRODUCT_1]} * (\text{price_equilibration[PRODUCT_1]} / \text{Price[PRODUCT_1]}) - \text{Products_offered[PRODUCT_1]}$$

The influence of the change in *Price* on the demand is modelled via the *Price-based_demand_change* flow, which is connected to the *Demand* stock. It is a bi-directional flow, meaning that it can both feed to and deplete the *Demand* stock. The equation for the *Price-based_demand_change* flow is defined based on the economic concept of the price elasticity of demand as follows:

IF Price = 0 THEN 0

ELSE

$$\text{demand} * \text{demand_elasticity} * (\text{price_equilibration} + \text{"cost-based_price_change"}) / \text{Price}$$

In addition to the own-price-based equilibration, the module also considers the effect of the price of a competing or complementary product on the own price of a specific product. This effect is incorporated in the model by deploying the concept of the cross-price elasticity. The *cross-price_demand_change* flow connects to the *demand* stock to capture this effect. The *cross-price_demand_change* flow is based on the multiplication of the percentual change in the price of the competing/complementary product by the *cross-price_elasticity* defined for the competing/complementary product. For instance, in the case of the *Circular plastics* the cross-price elasticity of *Recycled PET* is used for the calculation of the effect on the demand for virgin PET, as the secondary plastic materials and products are expected to be competing for the demand against the primary products. In this case, the *cross-price_demand_change* flow is defined as:

² In the case of the market for recycled/biorecovered products, the variable representing the supply affected by the price change is *Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery*, while in the case of the market for reused products, it is the *Desired_production_reuse* variable.

$cross_price_elasticity[PET]*demand[PET]*(DERIVN(Price[Recycled_PET];1)/Price[Recycled_PET])$

The non-equilibrium elements represent the factors with a causal structure outside of the assessed system that influence the market of the system. In general, they represent the effect of the global/international market on the market of the system.

A very important non-equilibrium elements that reflect the willingness to uptake circular strategies are *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* and *reuse_appreciation* variables. These two elements reflect the extent of appreciation for the products originating recycling/biorecovery and reuse, respectively. More specifically, the *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* determines what fraction of the total demanded 1st life product (demanded by both producers and the market) is desired to originate from recycling or biorecovery. The *reuse_appreciation* determines what fraction of the total demanded product (demanded by both producers and the market) is desired to originate from reuse. Hence, a specific array dimension called “*Total Products*” is defined for the appreciation variables to represent the combination of the primary, recycled/biorecovered and reused product of the same type. For instance, the virgin PET, recycled PET and reused PET would be represented by a PET class in the *Total Products* dimension.

The supply of the products is affected by the links of the *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* and *reuse_appreciation* to the *Desired_production*, *Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery* and *Desired_production_reuse* variables. More specifically, the *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* and *reuse_appreciation* partition the *non-eq_desired_product_stock* among the three aforementioned variables that represent the desired production. The *non-eq_desired_product_stock* represents the amount of the product that the producers within the assessed system wish to have in stock and offer on the market. It is defined exogenously per total product and its value should include all the primary, recycled/biorecovered and reused product of the same type (e.g., in the case of *Circular plastics*, it should include the desired stock of virgin PET and recycled PET).

The demand for the products is affected by the links of the *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* and *reuse_appreciation* to the *adjusted_demand_trends* variable. More specifically, the *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* and *reuse_appreciation* partition the *demand_trends* variable among the primary, recycled/biorecovered and reused alternatives of the product. For instance, the partitioning equation defining the *adjusted_demand_trends* variable for the “PET” class in the *Products* dimension in the *Circular plastics* example is defined as:

$$\text{SUM}(\text{demand_trends}[*;PET]) * (1-\text{"recycling/biorecovery_appreciation"}[PET])*(1-\text{reuse_appreciation}[PET])$$

The *demand_trends* is a variable that determines the demand for a specific total product type and market. Hence, it has two dimensions [Total_products; Markets] and the values for each class and

various points in time are defined exogenously and intrapolated/extrapolated to cover the entire simulation time. The *demand* stock is affected by the *adjusted_demand_trends* via the *demand_trends_change*, a non-equilibrium bi-directional flow, which is defined as a time-based change of the *adjusted_demand_trends* variable.

The *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* and *reuse_appreciation* variables can be both set to equal any value within the range of 0 to 1. It is, however, important to note that high *reuse_appreciation* values will eventually lead to low demand and for recycled/biorecovered products even if the *recycling/biorecovery_appreciation* is set close to 1. This is caused by the preference for the second life products in the system established by the high *reuse_appreciation* value.

The *Price* stock is influenced by the non-equilibrium flows *price_trends_flow* and *cost_based_price_change*. The *price_trends_flow* is a bi-directional flow that accounts for the effect of the change of the price of the product on an international market on the price of the product on the market of the system. It is defined as a time-based change in the *price_trends* variable. The *price_trends* is a multidimensional graphical variable that defines the development of the price of the *Products* for each point in time. It is based on the intrapolation of the input datapoints.

The *cost_based_price_change* is a bi-directional flow that represents the contribution of the price-setting by the producers to the resulting price of the product. The producer price-setting in the model is based on the concept of minimum and maximum margins that the producer wants to sell their products with. These margins reflect the generic commercial strategy of the producers with the aims of maximising the profit (the maximum margin would reflect the margin at which it is more profitable to sell the products at lower price, as the quantity sold would increase). The minimum margin is represented by the *minimum_production_margin* variable in the model, while the maximum margin is represented by the *maximum_production_margin* variable. The margins are expressed in relation to the *Price* and the *production_cost_factor* of the product. The *cost_based_price_change* is defined as follows:

```
IF ((Price[Product_7] - production_cost_factor[Product_7] * (1 + minimum_production_margin[Product_7])) < 0)
```

```
THEN Price[Product_7] - production_cost_factor[Product_7] * (1 + minimum_production_margin[Product_7])
```

```
ELSE
```

```
IF ((Price[Product_7] - production_cost_factor[Product_7] * (1 + maximum_production_margin[Product_7])) > 0) THEN  
production_cost_factor[Product_7] * (1 + maximum_production_margin[Product_7]) - Price[Product_7]
```

```
ELSE 0
```

The context-related elements affect the *Demand* stock via the *context-based_demand_change* flow. The *context-based_demand_change* is defined based on the change in the individual context indicators and the context-indicator-specific *context_demand_factor*. The *context_demand_factor* is a

variable that determines how much a change of the *Context* stock for a specific indicator translates to change in the *Demand* stock. It can be defined exogenous and also endogenously (if the ratios of initial states of the *Demand* and *Context* stocks are used). For instance, the *context_demand_factor* for the *Population* context indicator will determine how much the *Demand* stock changes with the change in the population of the assessed system.

Resources module

This module represents the resources that are available to individual value chain activities. The module accounts for non-renewable and renewable resources separately. The non-renewable resources module is depicted in Figure 17. In the case of non-renewable resources, the amount available to the value chain of the system is defined by the *Resources* stock. As per the model, this stock does not have any inflows and therefore it is only depleted until a possible total depletion at some point in time. The outflow that depletes the *Resources* stock the *resource_decay* flow. The amount of this flow is determined by a multi-variable linear equation. The variables used in the equation can be categorized as being either a *resource_factor* or a flow/stock corresponding to a value chain activity. The *resource_factor* is a variable that determines the amount of the *Resource* stock that is used per unit of the activity throughput in case of activities represented by flows (all except for use and purchased products). In the case of the value chain activities represented by stocks, the *resource_factor* determines the amount of the *Resource* stock that is used per unit of the products/materials in the stock. The formula for the *resource_decay* flow can be generalised as follows:

$$\text{SUM}(\text{value_chain_activity} * \text{value_chain_activity_resource_factor})$$

Sustainability assessment modules

In general, the SD model incorporates 3 modules addressing the assessment of the sustainability associated with the system. Each of these systems covers a specific part of the sustainability and features corresponding indicators. More specifically, the environmental impacts module covers the environmental sustainability of the system, the social impacts module covers the social sustainability, and the economic impacts module addresses the economic sustainability of the system. The modelling logic behind all three modules is very similar. In essence, linear relationships established between individual value chain activities and their impact factors are used to calculate the impacts. In general, the following value chain activities are used to calculate the sustainability impacts in the model:

- production (flow)
- product import (flow)
- product export (flow)
- purchased products (stock)
- unutilized wastage (flow)
- product use (stock)
- disposal (flow)
- composting (flow)
- littering (flow)
- collection for recycling/biorecovery (flow)
- recycling/biorecovery transformation (flow)
- collection for reuse (flow)
- reuse transformation (flow)

Environmental impacts assessment

The environmental impacts module is presented in Figure 19. In this module, the impacts associated with each of these value chain activities is calculated by multiplying the activity-specific *environmental_factor* by the activity flow of stock. The *environmental_factor* expresses the magnitude of impacts associated with the unit of throughput of a flow or the unit of the magnitude of a stock. The *environmental_factor* is a two-dimensional variable classified according to the [Environmental impact category; Product] array dimensions. Moreover, each value chain activity of the system has an *environmental_factor* defined for it. For instance, *disposal_environmental_factor[Climate change, PET]* determines what will be the climate change impact of treating 1 ton of PET by disposal. The following environmental impact categories are considered in the generic SD model:

- Global warming potential
- Abiotic depletion potential for non-fossil resources
- Total amount of solid waste disposal
- Total amount of organic waste produced
- Resource criticality assessment
- Acidification potential Accumulated Exceedance

- Eutrophication potential fraction of nutrients reaching freshwater end compartment
- Eutrophication potential fraction of nutrients reaching marine end compartment
- Eutrophication potential Accumulated Exceedance
- Formation potential of tropospheric ozone
- Abiotic depletion potential for fossil resources potential
- Water user deprivation potential deprivation
- Potential comparative toxic unit for ecosystems
- Potential comparative toxic unit for humans
- Land use Potential soil quality index
- Depletion potential of the stratospheric ozone layer
- Potential incidence of disease due to PM emission
- Potential Human exposure efficiency relative to U235 IRP
- Mean abundance of original species (GLOBIO)

Figure 19: Environmental impacts assessment module of the SD model.

The *environmental_factors* used in the model represent a semi-aggregated impact data, which have to be defined based on more granular LCA modelling on the level of unit processes. Within this framework, openLCA software in combination with LCA databases will be used for the modelling of the value chain activities on a more granular level. Moreover, the values of *environmental_factors* are expected to change over time, as a prospective LCA will be performed.

The overall environmental impacts associated with the system are represented by the *accumulated_environmental_impact* stock, which is accumulating the inflow from the *change_in_environmental_impacts* flow. The stock represents the environmental impacts associated with the environmental impact category and a specific product accumulated on a system level over time. On the other hand, the *change_in_environmental_impacts* flow represents the impacts associated with the environmental category and a product in a given time step of the simulation. The formula of the *change_in_environmental_impacts* flow can be generalised as:

$$\text{SUM}(\text{value_chain_activity}[\text{Product}] * \text{value_chain_activity_environmental_factor} [\text{Product}; \text{Impact category}])$$

Social impacts assessment

Social impacts assessment module is presented in Figure 20. It is modelled based on the same approach as in the case of environmental impact assessment module. The *wellbeing_factors* are two-dimensional variables [Social impact; Product] that are defined for each of the key value chain activities. The *wellbeing_factors* determine the magnitude social impact associated with the unit of throughput of a flow or the unit of the magnitude of a stock. They need to be defined based on a more granular analysis of the social impacts by conducting a S-LCA. Within this framework, a prospective analysis of the social conditions and activity variable will be conducted as a part of a prospective S-LCA. In this way, *wellbeing_factors* will be defined and then input to the SD model. The following social impact categories are integrated in the generic SD model:

- Accident rates at workplace
- Working time
- Trade union density
- Gender employment gap
- Gender pay gap
- Income quintile share ratio
- Fair salary
- Social security expenditure
- Violations of employment laws

Analogous to the environmental impacts assessment, the accumulated social impact on a system level is expressed by the *Human wellbeing* stock. Moreover, the time-step-specific impact is expressed by the *change_in_wellbeing* flow.

Figure 20: Social impact assessment module of the SD model.

Economic impacts assessment module

The economic impact assessment module is presented in Figure 21. The module consists of two parts, each assessing one specific indicator:

- Life cycle costing
- Value added of the system

The life cycle costing part of the module follows the same modelling principle as the environmental impact assessment and social impact assessment modules. That is, each of the key activities in the value chain is characterized by its own *cost_factor*. *Cost_factor* is a variable with one dimension [Products]. It expresses the incurred cost associated with each of the key value chain activities per unit of the flow throughput or stock magnitude. It is defined exogenously based on the data available, e.g., in the LCA databases such as ecoinvent.

Figure 21: Economic impact assessment submodule of the SD model.

The total accumulated cost incurred by the whole value chain on a system level is represented by the *cumulative_life_cycle_costs* stock. On the other hand, time-step-specific information on the life cycle costs of the individual products is indicated by the *life_cycle_costs* variable and the *life_cycle_costs_flow* flow (which equals the *life_cycle_costs* variable). The formula of the *life_cycle_costs* variable can be generalised as:

$$\text{SUM}(\text{value_chain_activity}[\text{Product}] * \text{value_chain_activity_cost_factor} [\text{Product}])$$

The added value indicator of the is indicated by the *Cumulative_added_value* stock, which represents net economic value created by the system cumulatively over the simulation time. This stock has one inflow that feeds to it (*Sales-created_value* flow) and one outflow, which depletes it (*life_cycle_costs_flow* flow). The *Sales-created_value* flow is defined as the sum of the *Price* multiplied by the *sale* volume for each product in the assessed system.

5.3.1.1.2 Populating the model with data

This step involves the entry of the collected data into the developed SD model. An automated approach towards the data entry is recommended, as the data requirements of the SD model can become significantly high. For instance, the generic SD model presented hereby was found to require more than 48000 data points to be entered into it. However, an analysis of the data requirements revealed that many of these datapoints can be set to zero, as they represent flows/activities which can be deactivated in the model. Hence, it is desirable to have a template editable in a table processor software (e.g., MS Excel) that automates the entry of the datapoints by e.g., using pre-defined values

for some of the parameters (these values can be linked to specific scenarios chosen) or by using some of the entered data points to calculate others.

A data entry template can be generated in the *Stella Architect* software that is used for the SD modeling in this framework. Adjusting and modifying such a template allows the modeller to automate the data entry process, while ensuring that the structure of the automated data entry template will be compatible with the SD software. Working with *Stella Architect* (*Main menu* → *Model* → *Import Data...*), the modeller is able to generate the template (*Make Template* button) and then link it to the model dynamically, as presented in Figure 22. Moreover, it is possible to select a specific import behavior based on the type of elements should be controlled by the template.

Figure 22: Interface for generating and linking a data entry template to the SD model in *Stella Architect* software.

5.3.1.1.3 Running the simulation and extracting the results

Once the SD model is populated with the correct data, the final step of running the model to generate a simulation of the model is performed. Before the SD model is being run, a few key run specifications should be adjusted to fit the assessment goal and scope the best. The interface of the *Stella Architect* software used to specify the run specifications is presented in Figure 23. The most important SD model run specifications are the simulation time (delimited by the *Start Time* and the *Stop Time* parameters) and the time of one simulation step (represented by the *DT* parameter in *Stella Architect*). It is recommended to set the time of one simulation step to be relatively low, as it determines how many iterative

calculations will be performed by the software. To capture the dynamics between the highly interconnected elements of the model (e.g., the links between the price, supply and demand in the market module), the number of iterative calculations should be sufficiently high. For instance, the time of one simulation step of 0.1 year was used in the preliminary *Circular Plastics* case simulation.

Figure 23: Run specifications interface of Stella Architect software.

Running the SD model generates numerical predictions for every element of the system during the simulation period with a resolution defined by the time of one simulation step. In practice, this will result in numerous indicators that can be used for the analysis of the system. However, the most important predictions for the sustainability and circularity assessment are those related to the sustainability indicators. Here the results related to the following stocks are key, as they reflect the accumulated impacts of the system level:

- *accumulated_environmental_impact* stock
- *Human wellbeing* stock
- *cumulative_life_cycle_costs* stock
- *Cumulative_added_value* stock

Summary of SAF requirements for step 3.1

- The structure of the SD model is defined, including all elements and their relationships.
- The SD model is populated with collected data.
- The model is run and the results are generated.

5.3.2 Validation

System dynamics validation

Validation is crucial in ensuring that the results generated by the SD model can inform decisions with sufficient reliability. The process of validating the developed system dynamics model was carried out in an iterative way and consisted of a set of tests directed towards model's structure and generated behaviour. This set of tests was formulated based on the review of the expert literature on system dynamics and can be classified into three categories: direct structure tests, structure-oriented behaviour tests, and direct behaviour tests (as categorized by Barlas, 1996). The outputs of the validation are to be used to identify the possible improvement that can be made to the model structure. Thus, the development of the model is interconnected with its validation in an iterative way following a general pattern: *structure validation* → *structure modification* → *behaviour validation* → *structure modification* → *structure validation* etc.

Direct structure tests

A general sequence for the validation of system dynamics models is to start with validation the system structure and then proceed to the validation of the model's behaviour (predictions) (Barlas, 1996). In general, structure validation (direct structure tests and structure-oriented behaviour tests) is essential and, combined with behaviour tests, enables high degree of confidence in the model. The direct structure tests carried out included:

Structure confirmation (verification):

In this test, the structure of the model is confirmed by the comparison of the form of the equations in the with the real-world knowledge. The validity of the form can be achieved by proving its coherence with either theoretical models or empirical knowledge of the system. Every equation of the model was scrutinized using the following procedure:

Evaluation of whether the equation is obvious, i.e., being derived simply of indisputably from other model elements (concept adopted from (Homer, 2014)). If the equation is obvious, it does not need any further verification.

Then a translation of the form of the equation into underlying assumptions is performed. These assumptions were then used to formulate validation questions based on the knowledge about the system in alignment with the following questions:

- Are all the relevant elements represented in the (sub)model?
- Are the elements included in the model relevant?
- Are there any missing relevant elements?
- Are all the relevant relationships represented in the model?
- Are the relationships included in the model relevant?
- Are there any missing relevant relationships?

The validation questions were formulated in the context of the whole module that an equation belongs to (e.g., *Production submodule*). This approach allows revealing any relevant elements or relationships that are not captured in the model's structure.

The evidence pertaining to the model's structure was collected from scientific literature. Form of the equations was verified directly by proving the existence of independently developed (and validated) models that represent certain modules of the model. For instance, *Renewable resources* submodule was developed in congruence with the logistic biological growth equation proposed by *Perman et al. 2003: Natural Resource and Environmental Economics*. Additionally, the form of the equations was also verified indirectly by the collection of the evidence confirming the validity of the model's structure in the context of the validation questions.

Minimal model structure confirmation:

The part of the structure confirmation when assessing the modifications of the SD model would be a minimal model structure test. This test would evaluate whether all parts that are essential for the develop SD model are inherently included in the SD model. These essential model elements are presented in section 5.1.8. The minimal model structure confirmation test should ensure the minimal model structure is complied with by the SD model.

Parameter confirmation (verification):

Each constant and variable of the model was assessed in terms of its correspondence to a real-world element (Bala et al., 2016)). In addition, the accuracy of the numerical values of the constant parameters, table functions and initial stock values was assessed.

Dimensional consistency test (verification):

This test was conducted to confirm that right-hand side and left-hand side of the equations are equal in units.

Boundary adequacy test:

This test evaluated whether all concepts and structures important for the decision-making process that the outcome of the model should inform are endogenous to the model (Quadrat-Ullah and Seong, 2010). The purpose of this test is to ensure that the model includes all variables and feedback loops of the system under the study that influence its dynamics and have policy implications (Bala et al., 2016). The test proved that all elements affecting the sustainability of the systemic transition to circular value chains, i.e., environmental, social and economic impacts associated with all life cycle stages, are endogenously generated in the model. Moreover, also the key elements driving the studied system's behaviour such as resources, supply, demand, price (competition), production, import, export, reuse and recycling are endogenous to the model.

Structure-oriented behaviour tests

This set of tests enables the validation of the causal structure and the identification of the elements that drive the model's behaviour.

Extreme conditions test

Evaluation of the model predictions under extreme conditions and comparison with anticipated outcome, e.g., consumption will become zero if the population is set to zero. The parameters selected to be subjected to extreme values were *demand*, *resources*, *collection_for_recycling/biorecovery*, *recycling_biorecovery_appreciation* and *renewable_resource_regeneration_rate*. The outcomes of these tests are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Validation test outcomes

Tested parameter	Tested value	Observed parameter	Expected outcome	Predicted outcome	Status
non-renewable resource stock	0	Production, Recycling/biorecovery transformation	immediate drop to 0	immediate drop to 0	passed
demand	0	sale	0	0	passed
Recycling/biorecovery appreciation	1	production (virgin), sale (virgin)	0	0	passed
Recycling/biorecovery feedstock	0	sale (recycled product)	eventual drop to 0	eventual drop to 0	passed
renewable resource regeneration rate	0	Production, Recycling/biorecovery transformation	0	0	passed

Feedback loop dominance test

Analysis to identify the most dominant feedback loops responsible for the model's behaviour at a given time. The output of this analysis is a *feedback loop dominance profile* that indicates which feedback loops dominate the model's behaviour over the modelled time period. The analysis can be performed using the Loops That Matter method integrated into the Stella software. The preliminary analysis of the most recent version of the SD model revealed that the feedback loops representing the relationship between *Price (of competing products)*, *Supply*, *Demand*, and *sale*. In further validation efforts, the most dominant loops will be identified and then compared with the empirical knowledge about the system to assess whether the model produces the behaviour for the right reasons.

Sensitivity analysis:

In the further validation efforts, sensitive elements of the model, i.e., the elements that model's behaviour is most sensitive to will be identified in the *Behaviour sensitivity test* described below. Usually, the system dynamics models are insensitive to most of the parameters and only a few parameters change the model behaviour considerably. The identified sensitive elements will then be evaluated in the context of the knowledge of the real system.

Direct behaviour tests:

In this set of tests, the model's ability to reproduce the behaviour of the real-world system is examined. The focus of this evaluation is on the ability to reproduce the behaviour patterns (and the specific characteristics such as amplitude, symptom generation, frequency etc. (Bala et al. 2016) rather than exact historical datapoints. Additionally, the tested elements should be endogenously generated by the model and be a good representation of the model's purpose.

Behaviour reproduction test:

Based on the comparison of the model predictions with empirical data about the system (Barlas, 1996). Several statistical methods can be employed, such as coefficient of determination (R^2) (Bala et al., 2016), Mean-square error analysis (Quadrat-Ullah and Seong, 2010), or Theil inequality analysis (Quadrat-Ullah and Seong, 2010). The further validation efforts in relation to this test will be focused on the collection of historical data, identification of the behaviour characteristics to be tested and statistical analysis.

Behaviour sensitivity test:

This test is based on the assessment of whether plausible changes in the parameter values of the model might cause the model to fail the behaviour pattern tests (described above). The following testing of model's behaviour sensitivity will include collection of data to determine the plausible ranges of *user-defined* parameters (considering the uncertainty of numerical values) and evaluation of the effect of the parameter change within these ranges on the model-generated behaviour.

Summary of SAF requirements for step 3.2

- The structure of the model is validated.
- The behaviour generated by the model is validated.
- The causal structure incorporated in the model is validated.
- The validation is performed iteratively to inform the development of the SD model.

5.3.3 Classification

Sustainability assessments can be performed on various levels. In most cases, the depth of a sustainability assessment study depends on the goal & scope. This defines what the results are purposed for, which life cycle stages are considered, or what data is required. The reliability and relevance of results for the target audience heavily depends on such modelling decisions. LCA studies are often accompanied by data quality scores. This gives the target audience an indication of criteria such as relevance and reliance. Such information is important when the sustainability assessment results are used for decisions with a bigger impact. For example, if one uses the sustainability assessment results as decision-making support in the implementation of an impactful policy, it might be important that the results are based on data that is reliable and validated. Having an index or score accompany the results of sustainability assessment thus allows the target audience to judge whether the results are suitable to support certain decision-making processes.

Therefore, this framework includes an index categorizes the results based on three dimensions:

- **Sustainability:** how well the metric and assessment can reflect the concept of sustainability as defined by the Brundtland commission.
- **Reality:** how well the model is backed by reality.
- **Scope:** how broad or narrow the scope of the model is.

The dimensions are scored from 1 to 5, depending on the defined criteria shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Scoring approach for scoring the sustainability assessment results.

The final score is the average of the score of the three dimensions.

In the end, the framework can be applied to all levels. Depending on the case certain score will be sufficient for the measurement of sustainability. Some sustainability indicators, for example, might not be relevant for certain regions or products. Meaning that not including these does not necessarily mean that “good” decisions cannot be made. It is essentially up to the modeller and the reader to determine whether assessment results match its purpose in a decision-making process. The index scoring is meant to support this matchmaking.

Summary of SAF requirements for step 3.3

- The model sustainability is scored.
- The model reality is scored.
- The model scope is scored.
- The average score is calculated.

5.4 Phase 4: Interpretation

The interpretation phase is an important part of the assessment. As the overview of the framework shows, it links to all other phases and therefore accompanies the assessment throughout its entirety. During all stages the modeller needs to interpret the findings and, if necessary, make certain adjustments. As an interlinked, system dynamics model is applied, results might be highly sensitive to certain

model structure changes. Furthermore, inputted data might dominate certain developments. It is up to the modeller to observe the calculated trends and make conclusion regarding the causes for the trends. Validating the model as described in section 3.2 will support the decision on model review action. The interpretation is thus an iterative process, which involves reviewing and revising the goal & scope and model structure as well as the data collected through the study.

In the end, interpreting the results will especially determine the recommendations in terms of the goal of the assessment. The overlying goal of this sustainability assessment framework is to conclude what circular economy strategy is the most suitable for the selected region in terms of the selected indicators. Results are calculated for the different scenarios. The modeller shall consider the results of each scenario and the associated trade-offs and derive recommendations. Based on the validation and the sustainability index results, conclusions can be made on the depth and reliability of the results. These shall be considered when formulating the recommendations.

Summary of SAF requirements for phase 4

- All elements of the framework are continuously revised and reviewed. Adjustments are made if needed.
- A sensitivity analysis is conducted.
- Results are analysed by linked developments to unambiguous determinants
- Key observations are documented.
- Trade-offs are considered when calculating results for the different scenarios.
- Strategy recommendations are made.

6 Summary and conclusion

The novel SAF combines several existing methods and tools to overcome some of the challenges of current sustainability assessment approaches. The link between these methods and the method for their collective application are regulated within this SAF. Taking inspiration from the standard application of an LCA, the SAF also takes on four phases: goal & scope, data collection, results calculation and interpretation. Yet, several additional concepts and features are included due to the systemic nature of the assessment tools. The goal & scope includes a model structure adjustment step that looks at the elements and links of the system dynamics model. Also, relevant scenarios are formulated based on the sector, products, and circular economy strategies. It e.g. becomes important to include policy scenarios if certain policies are expected to be introduced and will have a significant impact on the sector. Applying the tools is then done by entering the data collected and simulating results with the system dynamics model. Sustainability impact factors are pre-calculated using LCSA approaches and tools. The results are then validated and characterized in order to put them into perspective.

All in all, the modeller constructs an assessment pathway with the different elements of the framework. The goal of the study is the initiator, with the subsequent stages building the pathway to the ultimate result: key value chains assessed in terms of their sustainability to give recommendations for circular economy strategies. The interpretation phase essentially allows the modeller to revise the pathway in an iterative manner throughout the assessment so that the optimal pathway can eventually be determined.

The extensive framework evolved from the limitations seen in current sustainability assessment methods. With an SD model, several of these limitations can be overcome. Nevertheless, a system-based approach comes with several challenges. Dynamically modelling interweaved value chains quickly leads to a scope linked to heavy data requirements. The more determinants that are included, the more complex and less stable the model becomes. System dynamics allows one to model any system at levels of complexity. This makes the tools extremely flexible but at the same time open to modelling issues. The framework gives guidance and several methods to ensure the stability and transparency of conducting a sustainability assessment with system dynamics. Several segments of the framework, such as the validation of the model, mitigate some of the challenges. Throughout the rest of the project, the framework will be applied to the different key value chains in the project. This will help fine-tune and improve the novel approach, in order to enable a wider application in the future. This document is therefore a first iteration of the final guidance document and will be continuously updated throughout the project duration.

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8 Annex I

Table 5: Overview of elements of the SD model and their definition and explanation.

Parameters and variables	Equation	Explanation
Products offered	INIT + production – sale	the amount of products offered on the market
production	For primary production: $\text{MIN}(\text{capacity_rate_to_demand}, \text{resources_to_demand})$	the production is limited either by capacity (and demand through capacity rate) or by resources
	For sidestream production: $\text{production_sidestream_generation}[\text{Byproduct_1}]$	the sidestream production is entirely determined by the volume of the primary production and the production sidestream ratio
production sidestream ratio	User-defined	the ratio of generation of the sidestream based on the volume of the primary production (used to map the sidestreams to the primary products)
Production sidestream generation	$\text{production}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{production_sidestream_ratio}[\text{Product_1}; \text{Byproduct_1}] + \text{production}[\text{Product_2}] * \text{production_sidestream_ratio}[\text{Product_2}; \text{Byproduct_1}] + \text{production}[\text{Product_3}] * \text{production_sidestream_ratio}[\text{Product_3}; \text{Byproduct_1}] + \text{production}[\text{Product_4}] * \text{production_sidestream_ratio}[\text{Product_4}; \text{Byproduct_1}] + \text{production}[\text{Product_5}] * \text{production_sidestream_ratio}[\text{Product_5}; \text{Byproduct_1}] + \text{production}[\text{Product_6}] * \text{production_sidestream_ratio}[\text{Product_6}; \text{Byproduct_1}] + \text{production}[\text{Product_7}] * \text{production_sidestream_ratio}[\text{Product_7}; \text{Byproduct_1}]$	volume of each product produced multiplied by the production sidestream ratio
capacity rate to demand	IF $\text{production_capacity_rate}[\text{Products}] < \text{Desired_production}$ THEN $\text{production_capacity_rate}[\text{Products}]$ ELSE $(\text{Desired_production}[\text{Products}])$	selection of the limiting factor: either production capacity or demand

production capacity rate	User defined, time-dependent	Easily defined, this characteristic is a sum of individual production capacities of the companies in the economy
desired production	$\text{non-eq_desired_product_stock}[\text{Product_1}] * (1 - \text{recycling_appreciation}[\text{Product_1}]) * (1 - \text{reuse_appreciation}[\text{Product_1}]) + \text{Products_offered}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{supply_elasticity}[\text{Product_1}] * (\text{price_equilibration}[\text{Product_1}] / \text{Price}[\text{Product_1}] - \text{Products_offered}[\text{Product_1}])$	determining the desired production of the virgin products based on the partitioning of the desired product stock (first part of the equation) and the response to the price (via elasticity → second part of the equation, adjustment of the supply based on the elasticity and price, assuming that the supply would change only due to equilibration process, not due to change in price_trends)
product import	Product_import_rate	flow of products imported to the market of the system under study
product import rate	User-defined	rate of flow of products imported to the market of the system under study
product export	$\text{Products_offered} * \text{production_export_rate}$	flow of products exported from the market of the system under study
product export rate	User-defined	rate flow of products exported from the market of the system under study
non-eq desired product stock	User defined	represents the amount of the product that the producers would wish to have in stock and offer on the market

recycling/biorecovery appreciation	User defined	determines what fraction of the total demanded 1st life product (demanded by both producers and the market) is desired to originate from recycling or biorecovery
reuse appreciation	User defined	determines what fraction of the total demanded product (demanded by both producers and the market) is desired to originate from reuse
resources to demand	IF Resources[Products] > production_resource_factor[Products]*(Desired_production[Products]) AND Renewable_resources[Products] > production_renewable_resource_factor[Products] * Desired_production[Products] THEN Desired_production[Products] ELSE MIN(Resources[Products]/production_resource_factor[Products]; Renewable_resources[Products]/production_renewable_resource_factor[Products])	selection of the limiting factor for production: either demand or resources; Determines resource demand by checking if resources are available. The resource demand level is determined by the production demand
sale	IF Products_offered > demand THEN demand ELSE Products_offered	selection of the limiting factor of the sale of virgin plastics: either the product offer or demand
demand	INIT (=adjusted_demand_trends) + demand_trends_change + "price_based_demand_change" + "population-based_demand_change" + "cross-price_demand_change"	the stock of demand that get influenced by the change in the global demand trends, change in price, change in population and change in the price of the competing product(s)
demand trends	User defined	demand trends that correspond to the total demand for the product that fulfills a given function (i.e., regardless of whether it is from virgin (fossil-fuel) material or recycled, reused or bio-recovered). It is assumed that the substitution

		factor of the alternatives would be equal to 1.
adjusted demand trends	$SUM(demand_trends[*;Product_1])*(1-recycling_appreciation[Product_1])*(1-reuse_appreciation[Product_1])$	sum of the demand over individual markets, demand trends adjusted to the virgin/fossil product; the virgin and recycled product are always assumed to be 1st life → the virgin product competes with both recycled and reused product
	$SUM(demand_trends[*; Product_1])*(recycling_appreciation[Product_1])*(1-reuse_appreciation[Product_1])$	sum of the demand over individual markets, demand trends adjusted to the recycled/biobased product; the virgin and recycled product are always assumed to be 1st life → the virgin product competes with both recycled and reused product

	$SUM(demand_trends[*;Product_1])*(reuse_appreciation[Product_1])$	sum of the demand over individual markets, demand trends adjusted to the reused/2nd life product;→ the reused product competes with both recycled and virgin product
de- mand_trends_change	$DERIVN(adjusted_demand_trends; 1)$	time-change in the demand trends
"price-based_de- mand_change"	$demand*demand_elasticity*(price_equilibration+"cost_based_price_change")/Price$	calculated based on the concept of demand elasticity of a price, takes only the change of price due to equilibration and the change of the price due to production cost into consideration (not the change in the price_trends → this is supposed to be reflected in the demand_trends)
"context-based_de- mand_change"	TO BE DEFINED	
context demand factor	User-defined	
cross-price demand change	$cross_price_elasticity*de-mand*(DERIVN(Price;1)/Price)\{cross-price\ elasticity\ of\ the\ modeled\ product*demand\ of\ the\ modeled\ product*change\ in\ price\ of\ the\ competing\ product\}$	change in demand based on the change in the price of the competing product, modelled based on the concept of the cross-price elasticity
cross-price elasticity	User-defined	this parameter determines how much will the demand of a target product response to the percentual change in the price of the competing product
supply_elasticity	User defined	price elasticity of supply (%change supply/%change price)
demand_elasticity	User defined	price elasticity of demand (%change demand/%change price)
change_in_equilib- rium_price	$(demand-Products_offered)*Price/(supply_elasticity*((Products_offered))-demand_elasticity*demand)$	change in price needed to achieve equilibrium between demand and supply; (Demand(init) - Supply(init))*price(init)/(supply_elasticity*Supply(init)-demand_elasticity*(demand(init)))
price	$INIT+price_equilibration+price_trends_flow$	initial price is determined based on the price_trends and then changed based on the change in the price trends and based on the change needed to achieve

		equilibrium price, ASSEUMED: linear elasticities, relationship between local supply and demand having an effect on the price (however, this effect being limited)
price_equilibration	change_in_equilibrium_price* equilibrating_factor	change in price caused by the imbalance between demand and supply
price_trends_flow	DERIVN((price_trends), 1)	operator to derive time-based change of price_trends for the price stock
price_trends	User-defined	stock of demand, adjustment of the demand based on the demand elasticity and price
equilibrating_factor	User defined	factor that determines to what degree the system will try to achieve equilibrium price; also determines to what extent will local supply and demand determine the price of a commodity governed by global market
cost-based price change	IF ((Price-production_cost_factor*(1+production_margin))>0) THEN Price-production_cost_factor*(1+production_margin) ELSE 0	a flow to account for the influence of the production cost on the product's price; based on the assumption that the price has to reflect a minimum margin set by the producer; however, if the price is higher than what would correspond to this margin, it will not be decreased by the producers and this element will be equal 0
minimum production margin	User-defined	minimum margin that producers desire
maximum production margin	User-defined	maximum margin that producers desire (at this margin the producers prefer to decrease the price to maximize the profits)
key production resources cost	User-defined	the cost of the key resources used in the production (e.g., oil) per unit
key production resources factor	User-defined	the quantity of the key production resources used per the unit of production output
Purchased products	INIT + sale - indirect_utilization - direct_utilization - unutilized	stock of the products that have been sold; the products can be either utilized directly (through the product use) or

		utilize indirectly (outside of the model system) or wasted without being used
unutilized wastage/transport of sidestreams for recovery	$EoL_classified_unutilized_rate * Purchased_products$	this flow refers to the fraction of the purchased products that are wasted without being used AND this flow will also be used to send by-products to the EoL and recovery directly without going through the use stage
EoL-classified wastage rate	$disposal_rate[Product_1] * wastage_rate[Product_1]$	partitioning of the total wastage flow of the product into individual EoL classes
	$litter_rate[Product_1] * wastage_rate[Product_1]$	partitioning of the total wastage flow of the product into individual EoL classes
	$recycling/biorecovery_rate[Product_1] * wastage_EoL_classes[RecycBiorec1;Product_1] * wastage_rate[Product_1]$	partitioning of the total wastage flow of the product into individual EoL classes
	$reuse_rate[Product_1] * wastage_rate[Product_1] * wastage_EoL_classes[Reuse_1;Product_1]$	partitioning of the total wastage flow of the product into individual EoL classes
	$composting_rate[Product_1] * wastage_rate[Product_1]$	partitioning of the total wastage flow of the product into individual EoL classes
wastage rate	User defined	Fraction of the product that gets wasted without being utilized (e.g., in the case of food waste)
wastage EoL classes	User defined	Partitioning of the recycled/biorecovered and reused unutilized product into individual treatment pathways
disposal rate wastage	$1 - litter_rate - recycling/biorecovery_rate - reuse_rate - composting_rate$	Fraction of the unutilized product being treated through landfill/energy recovery
reuse rate wastage	User-defined	Fraction of the unutilized product being reused
recycling rate wastage	User defined	Fraction of the unutilized product being recycled
litter rate wastage	User defined	Fraction of the unutilized product being composted

composting rate wastage	User defined	Fraction of the unutilized product being littered
Indirect utilization	$\text{indirect_utilization_rate} * \text{purchased_products}$	referring to the amount of purchased products that are being used in other systems (e.g., fertilizer being used in agriculture or gas being used as a fuel in the steel production)
indirect utilization rate	User defined	ratio of the product being used in other product systems
direct utilization	$\text{Purchased_products} * \text{direct_utilization_rate}$	amount of the products being used directly (in the products system under study)
direct utilization rate	User defined	ratio of the products being used directly (in the products system under study)
Products in use	$\text{INIT} + \text{direct utilization} - \text{product decay}$	
product decay	$\text{Eol-classified_product_death}$	fraction of the products in use that reaches their end of life
product death	<pre> IF (TIME<=product_lifespan) THEN initial_product_death_rate*INIT(Products_in_use) ELSE DELAY(Direct_utilization; product_lifespan) </pre>	total amount of products that will go to EoL; before the product lifespan is reached in the simulation, fraction of the initial stock of Products_in_use will be used
initial product death rate	User-defined	fraction of the initial Products_in_Use stock that will be used to model product death before the simulation time reaches the product lifespan
product lifespan	User-defined	the average lifespan of a given product
EoL-classified death rate	$\text{disposal_rate}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{product_death}[\text{Product_1}]$	partitioning of the total flow of the product to EoL into individual EoL treatment classes
	$\text{litter_rate}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{product_death}[\text{Product_1}]$	partitioning of the total flow of the product to EoL into individual EoL treatment classes

	$\text{recycling/biorecovery_rate}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{death_EoL_classes}[\text{RecycBiorec1}; \text{Product_1}] * \text{product_death}[\text{Product_1}]$	partitioning of the total flow of the product to EoL into individual EoL treatment classes
	$\text{reuse_rate}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{product_death}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{death_EoL_classes}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Product_1}]$	partitioning of the total flow of the product to EoL into individual EoL treatment classes
	$\text{composting_rate}[\text{Product_1}] * \text{product_death}[\text{Product_1}]$	partitioning of the total flow of the product to EoL into individual EoL treatment classes
EoL classes	User defined	Partitioning of the recycled/biorecovered and reused unutilized product into individual treatment pathways
disposal rate	$1 - \text{litter_rate} - \text{recycling/biorecovery_rate} - \text{reuse_rate} - \text{composting_rate}$	Fraction of the product at EoL being treated through landfill/energy recovery
reuse rate	User defined	Fraction of the product at EoL being reused
recycling/biorecovery rate	User defined	Fraction of the product at EoL being recycled
litter rate	User defined	Fraction of the product at EoL being littered
composting rate	User defined	Fraction of the product at EoL being composted
Products at EoL	INIT + product decay – disposal – recycling – littering	stock of products at their end of life
EoL export	$\text{Products_at_EoL} * \text{EoL_export_rate}$	a flow of the products outside of the modelled system
EoL export rate	User-defined	the fraction of the products partitioned into EoL Classes at the EoL stock that gets exported outside the system
disposal	$\text{Products_at_EoL}[\text{Disposal}; \text{Products}] - \text{EoL_export}[\text{Disposal}; \text{Products}]$	amount of products disposed
composting	$\text{Products_at_EoL}[\text{Composting}; \text{Products}] - \text{EoL_export}[\text{Composting}; \text{Products}]$	flow of products at the EoL that get composted
collection for recycling/biorecovery	For RecycBiorec EoL classes: $\text{Products_at_EoL}[\text{RecycBiorec1}; \text{Product_1}] - \text{EoL_export}[\text{RecycBiorec1}; \text{Product_1}]$ For other EoL classes: 0	flow of products at EoL that get collected for recycling or biorecovery
collection for reuse	For Reuse EoL classes: $\text{Products_at_EoL}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Product_1}] - \text{EoL_export}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Product_1}]$ For other EoL classes: 0	flow of products at EoL that get collected for reuse

littering	<code>Products_at_EoL[Litter;Products] - EoL_export[Litter;Products]</code>	flow of products at EoL that gets littered
Recycling/biorecovery feedstock	<code>INIT + "collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"+ "additive_materials_for_recycling/biorecovery" - "recycling/biorecovery_loss" - "recycling/biorecovery_transformation"</code>	stock of the feedstock materials for recycling or biorecovery
"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"	<code>MIN(recycling_capacity[EoL_Class;Products]; recycling_resources_to_demand[EoL_Class;Products])</code>	the recycling is limited by either demand, resources or capacity
recycling/biorecovery capacity	<code>IF "recycling/biorecovery_capacity_rate"<"Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery"[Products]THEN "recycling/biorecovery_capacity_rate" ELSE "Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery"[Products]</code>	selection of the limiting factor: either recycling capacity or demand
recycling/biorecovery capacity rate	User defined	total capacity of recycling infrastructure

<p>recycling resources to demand</p>	<pre> IF "Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock"[EoL_Class]=0 THEN 0 ELSE IF (Resources[Products]) > ("recycling/biorecovery_transformation_resource_factor"[EoL_Class;Products])*"Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery"[Products] AND Renewable_resources[Products] > "recycling/biorecovery_transformation_renewable_resource_factor"[EoL_Class;Products])*"Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery"[Products] AND ("Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock"[EoL_Class]*recyclate_feedstock_mapping_factor[EoL_Class;Products]) > "recycling/biorecovery_efficiency_factor"[EoL_Class;Products])*"Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery"[Products] THEN "Desired_production_recycling/biorecovery"[Products] ELSE MIN(MIN((Resources[Products])/("recycling/biorecovery_transformation_resource_factor"); Renewable_resources[Products]/"recycling/biorecovery_transformation_renewable_resource_factor"[EoL_Class;Products])); ("Recycling/biorecovery_feedstock"[EoL_Class])*recyclate_feedstock_mapping_factor/"recycling/biorecovery_efficiency_factor"[EoL_Class;Products]) </pre>	<p>selection of the limiting factor: either the demand (on the producer's side - desired production) or resources (this includes both the non-renew and renew resources and the feedstock for recycling/biorecovery → calculated based on the recycling resource factor, recycling/biorecovery efficiency factor and desired recycling/biorecovery production)</p>
<p>Desired production recycling/biorecovery</p>	<p>For recycled products: "non-eq_desired_product_stock"[Product_1]*("recycling/biorecovery_appreciation"[Product_1])*(1-reuse_appreciation[Product_1])+Products_offered[Product_w_recycling_1]*supply_elasticity[Product_w_recycling_1]*(price_equilibration[Product_w_recycling_1]/Price[Product_w_recycling_1])-Products_offered[Product_w_recycling_1]</p> <p>For other products: 0</p>	
<p>recycling/biorecovery efficiency factor</p>	<p>User-defined</p>	<p>a constant determining amount of recyclates consumed per recycled product output, i.e., how efficient is the recycling (or biorecovery) in recovering the end product from the feedstock</p>

recyclate feedstock mapping factor	IF "collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"=0 THEN 0 ELSE "collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"/SUM("collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[EoL_Class;*]); later will be User-defined	Recyclate_feedstock_mapping_factor is used to partition EoL_Classes among the individual polymers. The values will be defined by the based on the data collected from project partners. Until then, real-time-fraction of individual polymers in each EoL Class in recycling flow (corresponding to the collection) is used.
recycling/biorecovery additives ratio	User-defined	a ratio that defines the amount of the additive materials for recycling to the materials collected for recycling
additive materials for recycling/biorecovery	SUM("collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[EoL_Class;*]) * "recycling/biorecovery_additives_ratio"	flow of the additional materials that need to be added to the products collected for recycling in order to carry out the recycling transformation
recycling loss factor	1-1/MEAN("recycling/biorecovery_efficiency_factor"[EoL_Class; *])	a factor that determines the fraction of the feedstock for recycling/biorecovery that gets lost during the transformation
reuse feedstock	INIT + "collection_for_reuse"+ "additive_materials_for_reuse" - "reuse_lossess" - "reuse_transformation"	stock of the feedstock materials for reuse
"reuse_transformation"	MIN(reuse_resources_to_demand; reuse_capacity)	the reuse is limited by either demand, resources or capacity
reuse capacity	IF reuse_capacity_rate<Desired_production_reuse[Products] THEN reuse_capacity_rate ELSE Desired_production_reuse[Products]	selection of the limiting factor: either reuse capacity or demand

reuse capacity rate	User defined	total capacity of reuse infrastructure
reuse resources to demand	<pre> IF Reuse_feedstock[EoL_Class]=0 THEN 0 ELSE IF (Resources[Products]) > (reuse_transformation_resource_factor[EoL_Class;Products])*Desired_production_reuse[Products] AND Renewable_resources[Products] > reuse_transformation_renewable_resource_factor[EoL_Class;Products]*Desired_production_reuse[Products] AND (Reuse_feedstock[EoL_Class]*reuse_feedstock_mapping_factor[EoL_Class;Products]) > reuse_efficiency_factor[EoL_Class;Products]*Desired_production_reuse[Products] THEN Desired_production_reuse[Products] ELSE MIN(MIN((Resources[Products])/(reuse_transformation_resource_factor[EoL_Class;Products]); Renewable_resources[Products]/reuse_transformation_renewable_resource_factor[EoL_Class;Products]); Reuse_feedstock[EoL_Class]*reuse_feedstock_mapping_factor/reuse_efficiency_factor[EoL_Class;Products]) </pre>	selection of the limiting factor: either the demand (on the producer's side - desired production) or resources (this includes both the non-renew and renew resources and the feedstock for reuse → calculated based on the reuse resource factor, reuse efficiency factor and desired reuse production)
Desired production reuse	<p>For reused products: "non-eq_desired_product_stock"[Product_1]*(reuse_appreciation[Product_1])+Products_offered[Product_w_reuse_1]*supply_elasticity[Product_w_reuse_1]*(price_equilibration[Product_w_reuse_1]/Price[Product_w_reuse_1])-Products_offered[Product_w_reuse_1]</p> <p>For other products: 0</p>	the amount that the producers of the reused product wish to produce
reuse efficiency factor	User-defined	a factor that determines how much of the feedstock for reuse has to be used to produce 1 unit of the reused product

reuse feedstock mapping factor	<pre>IF "collection_for_reuse"=0 THEN 0 ELSE "collection_for_reuse"/SUM("collection_for_reuse"[EoL_Class;*]); later will be User-defined</pre>	Reuse_feedstock_mapping_factor is used to partition EoL_Classes among the individual products. The values will be defined based on the data collected from project partners. Until then, real-time-fraction of individual polymers in each EoL Class in reuse flow (corresponding to the collection) is used.
additive materials for reuse	$SUM(collection_for_reuse[EoL_Class; *]) * reuse_additives_ratio$	flow of the additional materials that need to be added to the products collected for reuse in order to carry out the reuse transformation
reuse additives ratio	User-defined	a ratio that defines the amount of the additive materials for reuse to the materials collected for reuse
reuse loss factor	$1-1/MEAN(reuse_efficiency_factor[EoL_Class; *])$	a factor that determines the fraction of the feedstock for reuse that gets lost during the transformation
Resources	INIT - resource decay	stock of non-renewable resources

<p>resource decay</p>	<pre> production*production_resource_factor[Products] +products_import*products_import_resource_factor +production_export[Products]*production_export_re- source_factor[Products] +Purchased_products*purchased_products_re- source_factor +SUM("unutilized_wastage/transport_of_side- streams_for_recovery"[*;Products])*unutilized_wast- age_resource_factor +Products_in_use[Products]*product_use_re- source_factor[Products] +("recycling/biorecovery_transformation_re- source_factor"[RecycBiorec1; Products]*"recycling/bio- recovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec1; Prod- ucts]+ "recycling/biorecovery_transformation_re- source_factor"[RecycBiorec2;Products]*"recycling/bio- recovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec2; Prod- ucts]+ "recycling/biorecovery_transformation_re- source_factor"[RecycBiorec3;Products]*"recycling/bio- recovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec3; Prod- ucts]+ "recycling/biorecovery_transformation_re- source_factor"[RecycBiorec4;Products]*"recycling/bio- recovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec4; Products]) +("collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_resource_fac- tor"[RecycBiorec1;Products]*"collection_for_recy- cling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec1; Products]+ "collec- tion_for_recycling/biorecovery_resource_factor"[Recy- cBiorec2;Products]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecov- ery"[RecycBiorec2; Products]+ "collection_for_recy- cling/biorecovery_resource_factor"[RecycBio- rec3;Products]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecov- ery"[RecycBiorec3; Products]+ "collection_for_recy- cling/biorecovery_resource_factor"[RecycBio- rec4;Products]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecov- ery"[RecycBiorec4; Products]) + collection_for_reuse_resource_factor[Reuse_1; </pre>	<p>SUM(amount of each life cycle stage * the resource factor of each life cycle stage) → quantity of the non-renewable resources used over the whole life cycle of the product; Assuming that resources used are linearly proportional to the outputs of life cycle processes</p>
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	$\begin{aligned} & \text{Products}] * \text{collection_for_reuse}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Products}] + \text{collection_for_reuse_resource_factor}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] * \text{collection_for_reuse}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] + \text{collection_for_reuse_resource_factor}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] * \text{collection_for_reuse}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] \\ & + \\ & \text{reuse_transformation_resource_factor}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Products}] * \text{reuse_transformation}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Products}] + \text{reuse_transformation_resource_factor}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] * \text{reuse_transformation}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] + \text{reuse_transformation_resource_factor}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] * \text{reuse_transformation}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] \\ & + \\ & \text{SUM}(\text{EoL_export}[*; \text{Products}]) * \text{EoL_export_resource_factor}[\text{Products}] \\ & + \text{composting}[\text{Composting}; \text{Products}] * \text{composting_resource_factor}[\text{Products}] \\ & + \text{disposal}[\text{Disposal}; \text{Products}] * \text{disposal_resource_factor}[\text{Products}] \\ & + \text{littering}[\text{Litter}; \text{Products}] * \text{littering_resource_factor}[\text{Products}] \end{aligned}$	
resource factor	User defined	a factor determining how much non-renewable resource is consumed per unit of value chain processes
Renewable resources	INIT + regeneration - extraction	stock of renewable resources
regeneration	$\begin{aligned} & \text{regeneration_rate} * (1 - (\text{Renewable_resources} / \text{max_renewable_resources})) * \text{Renewable_resources} \\ & + \text{SUM}(\text{composting}[*; \text{Products}]) * \text{composting_renewable_resource_generation_factor} \end{aligned}$	amount of renewable resources regenerated; the regeneration is in general determined by the maximum capacity of the system, regeneration rate and the renewable resource stock + also composting is modelled to add to the renewable resource stock
extraction	$\begin{aligned} & (\text{SUM}(\text{production}) * \text{production_renewable_resource_factor}) + (\text{SUM}(\text{Products_in_use}) * \text{product_renewable_resource_factor}) + (\text{SUM}(\text{recycling}) * \text{recycling_renewable_resource_rate}) + (\text{SUM}(\text{disposal}) * \text{disposal_renewable_resource_rate}) \end{aligned}$	quantity of non-renewable resources consumed over the life cycle of the product; assuming that the quantity of resources extracted is linearly dependent on the outputs of the life cycle of the product

regeneration rate	User defined	rate at which the renewable resource stock is being regenerated
max renewable resource	User defined	the maximum amount of the renewable resource within the carrying capacity of the defined ecosystem
composting renewable resource generation factor	User defined	the factor expressing the amount of renewable resource generated per unit of waste composted
renewable resource factor	User defined	a factor determining how much renewable resource is consumed per unit of value chain processes
Accumulated environmental impact	INIT + change in environmental impact	environmental impact associated with individual products accumulated over the time of simulation
change in environmental impact	$\text{production[Products]} * \text{production_environmental_factor[Products;Environmental_impacts]}$ $+ \text{products_import[Products]} * \text{products_import_environmental_factor[Products;Environmental_impacts]}$ $+ \text{production_export[Products]} * \text{production_export_environmental_factor[Products;Environmental_impacts]}$ $+ \text{Purchased_products[Products]} * \text{purchased_products_environmental_factor[Products;Environmental_impacts]}$ $+ \text{SUM}(\text{"unutilized_wastage/transport_of_side-streams_for_recovery"}[*;Products]) * \text{unutilized_wastage_environmental_factor[Products;Environmental_impacts]}$ $+ \text{Products_in_use[Products]} * \text{product_use_environmental_factor[Products;Environmental_impacts]}$ $+ (\text{"recycling/biorecovery_transformation_environmental_factor"}[\text{RecycBiorec1; Products;Environmental_impacts}] * \text{"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"}[\text{RecycBiorec1; Products}] + \text{"recycling/biorecovery_transformation_environmental_factor"}[\text{RecycBiorec2; Products;Environmental_impacts}] * \text{"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"}[\text{RecycBiorec2; Products}])$	following an LCA logic: activity * characterization factor; a factor expressing environmental impact per unit of a value chain process is multiplied by the magnitude of a given process

	<p>Products]+"recycling/biorecovery_transformation_environmental_factor"[RecycBiorec3;Products;Environmental_impacts]*"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec3; Products]+"recycling/biorecovery_transformation_environmental_factor"[RecycBiorec4;Products;Environmental_impacts]*"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec4; Products])</p> <p>+("collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_environmental_factor"[RecycBiorec1;Products;Environmental_impacts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec1; Products]+"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_environmental_factor"[RecycBiorec2;Products;Environmental_impacts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec2; Products]+"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_environmental_factor"[RecycBiorec3;Products;Environmental_impacts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec3; Products]+"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_environmental_factor"[RecycBiorec4;Products;Environmental_impacts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec4; Products])</p> <p>+ collection_for_reuse_environmental_factor[Reuse_1; Products;Environmental_impacts]*collection_for_reuse[Reuse_1; Products]+collection_for_reuse_environmental_factor[Reuse_2;Products;Environmental_impacts]*collection_for_reuse[Reuse_2; Products]+collection_for_reuse_environmental_factor[Reuse_3;Products;Environmental_impacts]*collection_for_reuse[Reuse_3; Products]</p> <p>+ reuse_transformation_environmental_factor[Reuse_1;Products;Environmental_impacts]*reuse_transformation[Reuse_1; Products]+reuse_transformation_environmental_factor[Reuse_2;Products;Environmental_impacts]*reuse_transformation[Reuse_2; Products]+reuse_transformation_environmental_factor[Reuse_3;Products;Environmental_impacts]*reuse_transformation[Reuse_3; Products]</p> <p>+</p>	
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	$\begin{aligned} & \text{SUM}(\text{EoL_export}[*;\text{Products}]) * \text{EoL_export_environmental_factor}[\text{Products};\text{Environmental_impacts}] \\ & + \text{composting}[\text{Composting};\text{Products}] * \text{composting_environmental_factor}[\text{Products};\text{Environmental_impacts}] \\ & + \text{disposal}[\text{Disposal}; \text{Products}] * \text{disposal_environmental_factor}[\text{Products};\text{Environmental_impacts}] \\ & + \text{littering}[\text{Litter};\text{Products}] * \text{littering_environmental_factor}[\text{Products};\text{Environmental_impacts}] \end{aligned}$	
Environmental factors	User defined	a factor expressing environmental impact per value chain process magnitude
Human wellbeing	INIT + change in wellbeing	

<p>change in wellbeing</p>	<pre> production[Products]*production_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts] +products_import[Products]*products_import_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts] +production_export[Products]*production_export_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts] +Purchased_products[Products]*purchased_products_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts] +SUM("unutilized_wastage/transport_of_side-streams_for_recovery"[*;Products])*unutilized_wastage_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts] +Products_in_use[Products]*product_use_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts] +("recycling/biorecovery_transformation_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec1; Products;Social_impacts]*"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec1; Products]+ "recycling/biorecovery_transformation_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec2;Products;Social_impacts]*"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec2; Products]+ "recycling/biorecovery_transformation_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec3;Products;Social_impacts]*"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec3; Products]+ "recycling/biorecovery_transformation_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec4;Products;Social_impacts]*"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec4; Products]) +("collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec1;Products;Social_impacts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec1; Products]+ "collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec2;Products;Social_impacts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec2; Products]+ "collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec3;Products;Social_impacts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec3; </pre>	<p>change in the wellbeing as a direct result of the processes involved in the life cycle of the product; assumed that other variables of the model do not influence human wellbeing</p>
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	<p>Products]"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_wellbeing_factor"[RecycBiorec4;Products;Social_impacts]"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec4; Products])</p> <p>+ collection_for_reuse_wellbeing_factor[Reuse_1; Products;Social_impacts]*collection_for_reuse[Reuse_1; Products]+collection_for_reuse_wellbeing_factor[Reuse_2;Products;Social_impacts]*collection_for_reuse[Reuse_2; Products]+collection_for_reuse_wellbeing_factor[Reuse_3;Products;Social_impacts]*collection_for_reuse[Reuse_3; Products]</p> <p>+ reuse_transformation_wellbeing_factor[Reuse_1;Products;Social_impacts]*reuse_transformation[Reuse_1; Products]+reuse_transformation_wellbeing_factor[Reuse_2;Products;Social_impacts]*reuse_transformation[Reuse_2; Products]+reuse_transformation_wellbeing_factor[Reuse_3;Products;Social_impacts]*reuse_transformation[Reuse_3; Products]</p> <p>+ SUM(EoL_export[*;Products])*EoL_export_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts]</p> <p>+composting[Composting;Products]*composting_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts]</p> <p>+disposal[Disposal; Products]*disposal_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts]</p> <p>+littering[Litter;Products]*littering_wellbeing_factor[Products;Social_impacts]</p>	
factors	User defined	a factor expressing social impact per value chain process magnitude

<p>Life cycle costs</p>	<pre> production*production_cost_factor[Products] +products_import*products_import_cost_factor +production_export[Products]*production_ex- port_cost_factor[Products] +Purchased_products*purchased_products_cost_fac- tor +SUM("unutilized_wastage/transport_of_side- streams_for_recovery"[*;Products])*unutilized_wast- age_cost_factor +Products_in_use[Products]*product_use_cost_fac- tor[Products] +("recycling/biorecovery_transformation_cost_fac- tor"[RecycBiorec1; Products]*"recycling/biorecov- ery_transformation"[RecycBiorec1; Products]+"recy- cling/biorecovery_transformation_cost_factor"[Recy- cBiorec2;Products]*"recycling/biorecovery_transfor- mation"[RecycBiorec2; Products]+"recycling/biorecov- ery_transformation_cost_factor"[RecycBiorec3;Prod- ucts]*"recycling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBi- orec3; Products]+"recycling/biorecovery_transfor- mation_cost_factor"[RecycBiorec4;Products]*"recy- cling/biorecovery_transformation"[RecycBiorec4; Prod- ucts]) +("collection_for_recycling/biorecovery_cost_fac- tor"[RecycBiorec1;Products]*"collection_for_recy- cling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec1; Products]+"collec- tion_for_recycling/biorecovery_cost_factor"[RecycBio- rec2;Products]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecov- ery"[RecycBiorec2; Products]+"collection_for_recy- cling/biorecovery_cost_factor"[RecycBiorec3;Prod- ucts]*"collection_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBio- rec3; Products]+"collection_for_recycling/biorecov- ery_cost_factor"[RecycBiorec4;Products]*"collec- tion_for_recycling/biorecovery"[RecycBiorec4; Prod- ucts]) + collection_for_reuse_cost_factor[Reuse_1; </pre>	<p>Costs incurred over the life cycle of the product; SUM(amount of each life cycle stage * LCS cost factor)</p>
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	$\begin{aligned} & \text{Products}] * \text{collection_for_reuse}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Products}] + \text{collection_for_reuse_cost_factor}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] * \text{collection_for_reuse}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] + \text{collection_for_reuse_cost_factor}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] * \text{collection_for_reuse}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] \\ & + \\ & \text{reuse_transformation_cost_factor}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Products}] * \text{reuse_transformation}[\text{Reuse_1}; \text{Products}] + \text{reuse_transformation_cost_factor}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] * \text{reuse_transformation}[\text{Reuse_2}; \text{Products}] + \text{reuse_transformation_cost_factor}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] * \text{reuse_transformation}[\text{Reuse_3}; \text{Products}] \\ & + \\ & \text{SUM}(\text{EoL_export}[*; \text{Products}]) * \text{EoL_export_cost_factor}[\text{Products}] \\ & + \text{composting}[\text{Composting}; \text{Products}] * \text{composting_cost_factor}[\text{Products}] \\ & + \text{disposal}[\text{Disposal}; \text{Products}] * \text{disposal_cost_factor}[\text{Products}] \\ & + \text{littering}[\text{Litter}; \text{Products}] * \text{littering_cost_factor}[\text{Products}] \end{aligned}$	
cost factor	User defined	the cost incurred per unit of the activity (e.g., cost of producing 1 ton of plastic)
production cost factor	User defined + $\text{key_production_resources_cost} * \text{key_production_resources_factor}$	defined differently from other cost factors due to its use in the price determination
value added	Price-life_cycle_costs	the total monetary value generated by the system
Population	INIT+population_increase-population_decrease	
population increase	User defined, time-dependent	a flow corresponding to the increase of the population (birth and migration)
population decrease	User defined, time-dependent	a flow corresponding to the decrease in the population (death and migration)
Income	INIT + income change	Total income of the population in the assessed region
income change	User defined, time-dependent	a flow corresponding to the change in total income of the population

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